

standICT.eu 2026

ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe

FOLLOWING THE FELLOWS

**IMPACT REPORT FROM
FUNDED APPLICANTS TO
THE STANDICT.EU 2026
FELLOWSHIP PROGRAMME**

FIFTH OPEN CALL

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Disclaimer

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About StandICT.eu

The project is coordinated by [Trust-IT Srl](#) (IT) acting as a technical coordinator, and [Dublin City University](#) (IE) acting as financial coordinator, supported by its partners [AUSTRALO](#) (ES), [European Digital SME Alliance](#) (BE), [Fraunhofer](#) (DE) and [Open Forum Europe](#) (BE).

Acknowledgements

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Finally, we would like to thank all our **EUOS Technical Working Groups** (European Observatory for ICT Standardisation) **chairs** and **members** for their investment in gathering expertise and producing outstanding landscape reports of the standardisation status across different ICT sectors.

■ Foreword

The European Green Deal & the New Industrial Strategy for Europe call for a strong EU presence in international Standardisation development. The recent significant shifts in the geopolitical environment call for increasing the intensity of the EU presence in international standardisation committees. Building up a strong and sustainable pool of European Standardisation competent professionals who are ready to engage in European and International Standardisation is crucial. With this we are pleased to contribute to this already engaged community through **the “Following the Fellows” series Impact Reports, now in its fifth edition under the new StandICT.eu 2026 project**, continuing the work of the precursor edition, proving a tangible testimony of the impact generated by European ICT experts working in collaboration with international Standardisation Developing Organisations (SDOs), thanks to the financial support provided through the StandICT.eu 2026 Fellowship Programme, as a paramount part of the broader mission of the StandICT.eu 2026 Coordination and Support Action.

The main purpose of these regular publications is to display the work carried out by our fellows and illustrate the demonstrable outcomes that excellent research can make to both society and to the economy (SMEs or industry at large). Therefore, we attempt to substantiate how each effort on which the fellows are engaged provides a potential benefit to society and contributes to achieving specific, desired societal outcomes because of the ICT Standardisation efforts.

As we move forward, our commitment to bolstering the EU’s role in international standardisation remains strong. The “Following the Fellows” series is not only a testament to the achievements of our fellows but also serves as an inspiration and a call to action for future standardisation professionals. By highlighting the critical work of these individuals, we aim to underscore the importance of ICT standardisation in driving innovation, ensuring competitive advantages, and contributing to the sustainability and resilience of society and the economy at large.

We invite the standardisation community, policymakers, industry stakeholders, and all interested parties to engage with the insights and findings presented in these reports.

Silvana Muscella

StandICT.eu 2026 Project Coordinator
& CEO, Trust-IT Srl

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■ Introduction

This report marks the fifth batch of funded fellows under the StandICT.eu 2026 Programme. It shares perspectives and the first results of the fellowships that were financed by the open call #5¹.

Our team is delighted to showcase the fifth series of StandICT.eu 2026 fellowship stories of the funded experts detailing the addressed standards and ICT landscapes, and how these will fill in the identified gaps and impact the related stakeholders and society. The results obtained by our fellows fully respond to many of the objectives set out in the EU Strategy on Standardisation. They mainly prioritise and address standardisation needs in strategic ICT areas, enhance European leadership in global standards, support innovation and improve the overall integrity of the European standardisation system.

Standards are at the core of the EU Single Market and global competitiveness and play a fundamental (even if sometimes invisible) function in our daily lives. They can ensure the interoperability of products and services, reduce costs, improve safety, and foster innovation.

At the same time, standards act as powerful drivers for innovation and growth by helping researchers bring their innovation to the market and spread technological advances, as standards make their results transparent and ensure high quality. One of the critical purposes of StandICT.eu 2026 is to support the activity of European ICT experts to contribute to the modernisation and consolidation of the European standardisation system as well as to the valorisation of their research outputs, to efficiently respond to the EU's ambitions towards different thematic ICT areas, such as Metaverse and Digital Product Passport, which were the focus of the announcement of the 5th Open Call.

The primary purpose of this document is to share the results attained through the work carried out by the funded experts and to showcase the most relevant outcomes, creating awareness of the potential impact and repercussions of such effects on commerce, industry, governmental policies and strategies and society. This open call is the fifth out of nine StandICT.eu 2026 Open Calls. Each open call will have a dedicated impact report demonstrating the key findings, contributions, and observations with the StandICT.eu community, the European Commission, the Multi-Stakeholder Platform for ICT Standardisation, the SDOs, and even beyond, all interested actors of our ever-growing StandICT.eu community.

In this funding batch, **in total, 37 fellowships** were granted, tackling the five policy areas as defined in the ICT Standardisation Rolling Plan 2024²:

- ▶ **Foundational drivers:** 13 fellowships focusing on Cybersecurity (11 fellowships), Privacy (1), and Data Economy (1).
- ▶ **Key enablers and security:** 13 fellowships focusing on Artificial Intelligence (8 fellowships), 5G/6G (1), electronic identification (3), and Quantum technology (1).
- ▶ **Innovation for Digital Single Market:** 4 fellowships focusing on Blockchain and DLT (2 fellowships), Fintech (1) and Smart cities (1).
- ▶ **Sustainable growth:** 5 fellowships focusing on Smart grids and smart metering (2), Circular Economy Including Digital Product Passport (1), ICT Environmental Impact (1), and Digitisation Of European Industry (1).
- ▶ **Societal challenges:** 2 fellowships focusing on eHealth.

1 <https://www.standict.eu/standicteu-2026-5th-open-call>

2 <https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/collection/rolling-plan-ict-standardisation/rolling-plan-2024>

Overview of the Open Call #5

The fourth open call was running from the 24th of Jun until the 23rd of August 2024. It received a record number of 117 applications, of which 37 were selected for funding, with an overall 325 544€ granted.

The StandICT.eu Open Calls target European ICT standardisation experts contributing to the international SDOs, work groups and/ or technical committees at any of the priority topics, as taken from the Rolling Plan for ICT Standardisation. Due to their current strategic importance at the EU level, applications focusing on the issues of Metaverse and Digital Product Passport are highly encouraged. However, this open call was open for applications tackling a broad range of ICT domains (as encompassed in the ICT Rolling Plan for Standardisation) and treated equally valid.

Fellowship Profiles

The funded applications offer a large geographic spectrum with 15 different EU or associated countries (with most experts from Spain, Belgium, France, and the United Kingdom). 24% of the funded experts are female, reflecting the broader context of ICT and standardisation professionals, where most workers are male. Moreover, 30% of the financed fellows are new to the StandICT.eu programme, and the remainder are returning fellows who have already benefited from a funded StandICT.eu fellowship.

The retained fellowships are represented by a balance across the key technologies and a wide spectrum of SDOs that will benefit from the competence and expertise of the applicants. As outlined in the figure below, a large portion of the granted fellows have chosen their focus across various horizontal and vertical ICT areas; the most popular areas in this batch include artificial intelligence, cybersecurity, and electronic identification. Moreover, this funding batch is marked by various vertical ICT areas the fellowships cover, namely smart grids and blockchain technologies.

Figure 1 - Overview of the #5 Open Call key results and insights

Engaged SDOs, Organisations and European Projects

65% of the fellows' activity contributes to the activities of Committees or Working Groups operating in global SDOs including ITU, IEC, IEEE, IETF, ISO, ISO/IEC while the remainder works with European Standardisation Organisations (ESOs), covering ETSI, CEN, CEN/CENELEC. As you will see in the forthcoming fellowship stories, the funded fellowships contribute to the development of new standards and revising existing ones. Some of the funded activities are dedicated to supporting the continuous work of (co-)chairs and (co-)conveners across varied standardisations, working groups and technical committees.

Finally, 12 European funded and innovation research projects (see Table 1) are related to the engaged work in the OC#5 fellowships, focusing on different horizontal and vertical technologies.

Project name	ICT Area	Funding Programme	Related StandICT.eu Fellows
NEO-CYCLE	Circular Economy, ICT Environmental impact	Horizon Europe	Leandro Navarro
HARPOCRATES - Federated Data Sharing and Analysis for Social Utility	Privacy	Horizon Europe	Nicolae Paladi
TITAN : Trusted environments for confidential computing and secure data sharing:	Privacy	Horizon Europe	
GLocalFlex : A Global as well as Local Flexibility Marketplace to Demonstrate Grid Balancing Mechanisms through Cross-sectoral Interconnected and Integrated Energy Ecosystems enabling Automatic Flexibility Trading	Smart Grids	Horizon Europe	
IMPACT Data	eHealth	National Institute of Health Carlos III and ERDF	Carlos-Luis Parra-Calderón
Met4EVCS : Metrology for electric vehicle charging systems	Smart Metering	Metrology Partnership	Marco Azpúrua
ACCRA EU : Agile Co-Creation of Robots for Ageing	Robotics	Horizon2020	Amelie Gyrard

Project name	ICT Area	Funding Programme	Related StandICT.eu Fellows
SOLARIS - Strengthening democratic engagement through value-based generative adversarial networks,	Digital skills	Horizon Europe	Piercosma Bisconti Lucidi
SYNTHEMA - Synthetic generation of hematological data over federated computing frameworks	eHealth	Horizon Europe	
LUCIA - Understanding Lung Cancer related risk factors and their Impact	eHealth	Horizon Europe	
AI4HOPE	Artificial intelligence, eHealth	Horizon Europe	
The Human-Tech Nexus - Building a Safe Haven to cope with Climate Extremes #101073957	ICT Environmental impact	Horizon Europe	Marios Angelopoulos

Now, we are delighted to share with you the insights from our granted fellows' work – and we genuinely hope that these results encourage you to get involved in our StandICT.eu community and join our Fellowship Programme under our forthcoming Open Calls, the European Observatory for ICT Standards (EUOS) - via the Technical Working Groups (TWGs) delivering up-to-date landscape and gap analysis, and finally Standards Academy training future experts in ICT Standardisation.

Together, we shape and reinforce the European and international ICT standardisation arena!

1. Foundational Drivers

Contribution to e-identification and e-authentication at CEN/CLC/JTC 13 & ISO/IEC JTC1/SC 27 WG5's

Christophe Stenuit
CEO, Viewconcept.be
Belgium

Sector

Cybersecurity

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO/IEC JTC 1 SC27 WG5 Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection, Working Group 5 on Identity management and privacy technologies
CEN/CENELEC JTC13 WG5 Cybersecurity and Data Protection, Working Group 5 on Data Protection, Privacy and Identity Management

Role

Member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

My fellowship aims to positively influence the European market and its infrastructures by benefiting from international contributions (e.g. ISO/IEC) in the controlling of civil security and the protecting of e-identity and e-privacy. I also contributed to enhancing existing references, and encouraged promoting the use of these references through adoption in the European market.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

With this fellowship, my work in the engaged standardisation groups contributes to ease the implementation of e-identity and e-privacy developments. The scope of this fellowship includes proposing and reviewing standards. In this sense, progress was made on the following ICT standards:

- ▷ ISO/IEC 24760-1 about identity management terminology and concepts
- ▷ ISO/IEC 24760-2 about identity management architecture
- ▷ ISO/IEC 24760-3 about identity management practices
- ▷ ISO/IEC 24760-4, about identity management and credentials, authenticators and authentication
- ▷ ISO/IEC 29146 about A framework for access management
- ▷ ISO/IEC 29115 about Entity authentication assurance framework
- ▷ Integration of the referred standards with their amendments
- ▷ Adoption of the referred standards as prEN
- ▷ Other supporting activities were also carried out, e.g. contributions on supporting standardisation activities in relation to, as part of the ISO JTC1 SC27 WG5:
 - ▷ AG5 on strategy
 - ▷ Development of threats associated with digital authentication and possible controls

- ▷ Analysis of identification and authentication processes
- ▷ And as part of the CEN/CLC/JTC 13/WG 5:
- ▷ Contribution to the establishment of a Liaison Statement of ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27 WG 5 to CEN-CENELEC JTC13.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

SME are better aware of risks and of controls required in IT and information protection. Recent EU GDPR, eIDA2 regulations and NIS-2 directives developments impose a different view on IT risks, information security, data privacy protection and identity management controls, and by this a different awareness of the consequences that may fall down improper compliance to good practices. Good standard references help establish confidence and maturity improvement in matters yesterday far from SMEs' concerns.

Impact on Society

My contribution to the ongoing standardisation projects has societal impact on three core areas, including:

- ▷ Secure societies - protecting freedom and security of Europe and its citizens: Supporting standards on e-identity and e-privacy information management ensures identity information lifecycle, identification, bound proofed identity information and authentication of citizens and societies are in place before authorized accesses to services is provided without compromising their privacy;
- ▷ Cybersecurity, network and identity information security: Standards on reference architectures around e-identity and e-privacy management ensure information infrastructure has the required controls in place to protect citizens and societies while accessing and using provided services;
- ▷ ePrivacy protection: Data protection good practice ensures any risk on identity information is mitigated during the processing of the information.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

This fellowship has two major axes: one part of its objectives is to support systematic reviews, revisions, and amendments of existing work items, and the other part is to support the adoption and the publicity of these work items at EU market, and by this guaranteeing the sustainability of existing references in a changing world.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, I have contributed to several technical reports in development of new standards, recommendations for revised standards, common terminology and reference material.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

Most developed standards are achieving maturity. Some work items are still at draft stage. Some others are nearly published or being published.

Online references related to the fellowship work

www.iso.org/committee/45306.html

https://standards.cenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:7:0:::FSP_ORG_ID:2307986&cs=1BFE244DDA2A68D1B5C93795034A8DD05

Advance Biometric System-On-Card (ISO/IEC 17839) Standard improvement

Pavel Cuchriajev

Technical expert contributor, Standard Norge
Lithuania

Sector

Cybersecurity

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO/IEC SC17 WG11 Application of biometrics to cards and personal identification

Role

Member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

The fellowship addresses gaps, priorities, and challenges in ICT standardisation through several key actions:

- ▷ Advancing BSoC Standards: Enhancing ISO/IEC 17839 series, particularly ISO/IEC 17839-1, -2, and -3, to ensure relevance in evolving BSoC technology.
- ▷ Interoperability and Compliance: Promoting consistent practices and compliance across sectors, fostering interoperability, especially among SMEs.
- ▷ Privacy Preservation: Safeguarding citizens' privacy, particularly in Europe, by storing biometric data exclusively on secure personal devices.
- ▷ Industry Engagement: Encouraging industry collaboration in the standardisation process, addressing declining expert participation.
- ▷ Technology Advancements: Incorporating recent technological developments and usability insights into BSoC standards to maintain relevance.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

The funded application significantly contributes to the ICT standards landscape by advancing the Biometric System-on-Card (BSoC) standards, particularly within the ISO/IEC 17839 series. By enhancing these standards, the application ensures BSoC technology aligns with industry best practices, promotes interoperability, and addresses emerging challenges. The application's involvement in ISO/IEC SC17 WG11 facilitates collaboration among industry stakeholders, promoting the adoption of standardized BSoC solutions. Specific ICT standards addressed include ISO/IEC 17839 series, ISO/IEC 24787, and ISO/IEC 7816-11. These standards define essential requirements for BSoC technology, ensuring secure identification and transaction authorisation while preserving privacy. By contributing to the development of these standards, the funded application plays a pivotal role in shaping the ICT standards landscape, promoting innovation, security, and interoperability in BSoC technology.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

Yes, my contribution impacts European SMEs by providing clear guidelines for implementing Biometric System-on-Card (BSoC) technology. Standards promote interoperability, reduce costs, enhance trust, and foster innovation, enabling SMEs to compete effectively, access markets, and build credibility.

Impact on Society

The work supported societal impacts by enhancing security and privacy, facilitating access to services, supporting digital transformation, promoting innovation and economic growth, and protecting individual rights in the digital age. The driving force behind the standards largely comes from European entities. It is crucial to advocate for European industry interests within this standard series to ensure the benefits of improved privacy and interoperability for European citizens. These factors contribute to enhanced privacy and a diversified landscape, reinforcing the significance of openness and interoperability.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I have contributed to the development of ISO/IEC 17839 standards, specifically -1, -2, and -3: provided comments, reviewed standard documents and disposition of comments.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Not directly, but I did provide comments on new editions of ISO/IEC 17839 standards and send them to the editor and co-editors.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

While work on the ISO/IEC 17839-2 project is completed, there is still more work to be done on maturing ISO/IEC 17839-1/17839-3 before they can be promoted to next stages. Discussions will be continued in next working group meetings.

Online references related to the fellowship work

www.iso.org/committee/45144.html

www.iso.org/committee/45144/x/catalogue/p/0/u/1/w/0/d/0

www.iso.org/standard/87667.html?browse=tc

www.iso.org/standard/87555.html?browse=tc

Support for Standardization of Secure Computing Methods

Thomas Loruenser
Researcher, Independent
Austria

Sector

Cybersecurity

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO/IEC JTC1 SC27 WG2[LM1] Cryptography and Security Mechanisms
ASI AG00127 Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection

Role

Expert Member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

My fellowship project is dedicated to supporting the standardisation of secure multiparty computation (MPC) in ISO/IEC and related technologies for secure computation. MPC is a cryptographic technique that allows computation on encrypted data and is expected to be an enabling technology for privacy-preserving collaboration in emerging data spaces and data ecosystems. The technology has been researched for decades, and recent scientific advances have led to many practical applications in real-world scenarios. Thus, it is an emerging technology with strong industry support and many large industry players are already adopting it.

The standardisation effort in this project is intended to help advance the standardisation of secure multiparty computation in ISO/IEC, which was initiated years ago by the experts from Austria and Japan. It builds on previous work (ISO/IEC 4922 parts 1 and 2) and supports the continuation within ISO but also beyond. Furthermore, to increase the impact, exploitation activities towards European data spaces through Gaia-X and the International Data Space Association will also be carried out. In addition, standardisation of related methods in ISO, such as oblivious transfer and fully homomorphic encryption, will be monitored and supported.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

This project helps me to continue my support of a previously initiated series of standards on secure multiparty computing. It allows me to further increase my focus on standardisation of privacy-enhancing technologies (PET) within ISO and to increase the contributions of the Austrian Standards Institute (ASI) to international standards. In addition, it helps me to leverage standardisation activities towards governance bodies developing standards for emerging data spaces in Europe.

In particular, I will contribute to the new Part 3 of MPC (ISO/IEC AWI 4922-3) and ensure alignment with existing parts. In addition, I will support the establishment of a new work item on oblivious transfer, all coordinated through concerted ISO and ASI activities. Finally, I will help to promote the integration of privacy-enhancing technologies for data spaces through the Gaia-X Hub in Austria.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

The work is expected to directly contribute to increasing the real-world uptake of advanced privacy-enhancing technologies, thereby advancing the state of the art in this area and helping to preserve the privacy and data sovereignty of European SMEs and ultimately citizens. In this sense, it addresses the need for innovation in cryptography to address modern use cases in emerging data ecosystems (e.g. Gaia-X) or large-scale networked systems (e.g. Internet of Things). In addition, a significant number of European SMEs working on the commercialisation of MPC and PETs in general will benefit from the results of the project (Sharemind, Partisia, Unbound, ...).

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I directly support part 3 of a new standard for secure multiparty computation (ISO/IEC AWI 4922-3) and the development of a standard for oblivious transfer (ISO/IEC AWI 25330).

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

No.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

To ensure the sustainability of previous activities on MPC (ISO/IEC 4922-1 and -2), continued support for part 3 should be established (ISO/IEC AWI 4922-3), as well as support for alternative technical approaches such as oblivious transfer (ISO/IEC AWI 25330), which is in the process of being standardized. In addition, alignment with ongoing activities of other SDOs would be highly desirable, as well as exploitation through data ecosystem governance bodies (e.g. Gaia-X and IDSA).

Online references related to the fellowship work

<https://committee.iso.org/home/jtc1sc27>

www.iso.org/standard/80508.html

www.iso.org/standard/80514.html

<https://www.iso.org/standard/87557.html>

<https://www.iso.org/standard/89943.html>

<https://www.mpcalliance.org/>

<https://gaia-x.eu/>

<https://internationaldataspaces.org/>

Participation in the standardisation work at the ESOs for the Cyber Resilience Act proposal

Octavian Popescu

Consultant researcher, EUCOMREG
Belgium

Sector

Cybersecurity

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

CEN / CENELEC JTC13 Cybersecurity and data protection WG9 Special Working Group on Cyber Resilience Act
ETSI TC CYBER

Role

Member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

As this is the 1st time cybersecurity legislation encompasses the entire lifecycle of products and services, the apparent gap is the need for more history regarding the implementation of such legislation. Hence, the priority of this work is to ensure that the first three horizontal standards should constitute the framework for the vertical standards.

The challenge is that everything needs to fit the purpose of the Cyber Resilience Act (CRA). While there is a vast body of literature relating to the technological, economic, societal, and even some legal aspects, no texts deal with how to comply with the CRA.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

I am active in CEN-CENELEC JTC13 WG9 and in ETSI TC CYBER. The proposed standardisation deliverables in Working Group 9 are related to the horizontal standards dealing with the definitions in the CRA, the vulnerabilities and reporting, methods for risk assessment, and the formulation of essential requirements correspondingly. This fellowship addresses the preliminary or exploratory activities for the standardisation work to be produced for the CRA.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

By its nature, the CRA covers all products with digital elements, and therefore, all supply chain segments are in it, including SMEs, and the European SMEs and societies are at the forefront. A successful and clear standardisation deliverable is the outcome of this standardisation process.

Impact on Society

In the framework of the CRA, the aim of the European Commission is an overall improvement of the network cybersecurity and related features protecting personal data and the user's privacy. When the proposed regulation enters into force, software and products connected to the internet would bear the CE marking to indicate they comply with the new standards.

In this spirit, the CRA-related standardisation work produces instructions for manufacturers of devices with digital elements explaining that they will now have to include technical features to improve the level of cybersecurity of such devices before placing them on the European market.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, the first three horizontal standards requested in the draft CRA Standardisation Request are in the remit of the JTC 13 WG 9 and its 3 Project Teams, which I am currently activating.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

I contributed to the draft work document for the proposed work item.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

While the CRA is in the process of adoption in the EU, the next step is the CRA Standardisation Request, wherein the standardisation activities and their schedules will be proposed, and only after that the standards shall be finalised and eventually published.

Online references related to the fellowship work

https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:7:0:::FSP_ORG_ID:2307986&cs=1BFE244DDA2A68D1B5C93795034A8DD05

Methods for cybersecurity evaluation and testing under RED cybersecurity essential requirements

Octavian Popescu

Consultant researcher, EUCOMREG
Belgium

Sector

Cybersecurity

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ETSI TC CYBER

Role

Member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

My fellowship addresses the need for guidelines regarding the topic of cybersecurity compliance as requested in the Radio Equipment Directive Delegated Act.

I aim to help firstly the SME manufacturing community to answer the questions related to the applicability of the requirements to the systems they place on the EU market, and hopefully to evaluate their cybersecurity preparedness for the purpose of complying with the RED Art. 3.3 requirements.

As a general priority, I work towards contributing to the production of guidelines, clarifying the steps to be taken in order to evaluate the state of compliance of radio equipment with the cybersecurity legal constraints for placing the equipment on the EU single market. These constraints are expressed in a high-level fashion by RED Article 3.3 d, e, f essential requirements.

While the best option for the SME community is to have the information regarding their product compliance readily available in one single guide this seems to be very difficult to achieve at this point in time. A significant obstacle is the fact that the CEN-CENELEC JTC13 WG8 technical committee tasked with producing the RED DA deliverables is currently dormant, and the ETSI TC CYBER technical committee is unsure of how best to deliver on this topic considering that they were not tasked with it.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

With this fellowship, I contribute to the production of usable methods of testing for cybersecurity compliance with RED Art. 3.3 d, e, f, and in general of cybersecurity evaluation protocols for use by the industry at large and SMEs in particular. It is important that these protocols are based whenever possible in the harmonised EN standards, and that they can be used by the radio communications equipment manufacturers and all other stakeholders in order to evaluate their equipment for the purpose of legal compliance to the cybersecurity requirements and therefore ultimately to improve their response to threats. My work is around the standards EN 18031-1, 2, 3 and EN 303 645.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

Firstly, I represent and construct my work mostly from a point of view based on my work in the SME world. Besides the general accessibility of usable protocols based on the harmonised standards for the European SME community, I also want to contribute to the clarification of the test methods applicable in conjunction with the harmonised European standards. This is currently an area of some debate with the experts engaged in discussions around the scope and limitations of the RED and its Delegated Act.

When writing my contributions to the standardisation debates, I aim towards making them as accessible as possible while staying sufficient for the compliance with the legal requirements.

Impact on Society

In the cybersecurity domain, threat modelling and risk assessment deal with unknowns and this is another area where I believe I can contribute. I also would propose to concentrate on the measurability and testability of the cybersecurity aspects resulting from the risk analysis as applied in a radio communication ecosystem.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

I am not contributing to the creation of new standards but rather encouraging the adoption of existing ones. I contribute to the production of guidelines, clarifying the steps to be taken in order to evaluate the state of compliance of radio equipment with the cybersecurity legal constraints for placing the equipment on the EU single market.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, my contributions are included in a single deliverable in the form of a guideline for the RED DA. This is still under development.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

As explained above, ideally this project would be to produce a single deliverable in the form of a guideline for the RED DA. Given the circumstances, I have several contributions to different NWI. My contributions are aiming at clarifying different ideas for protocols regarding cybersecurity evaluation

Online references related to the fellowship work

 www.etsi.org/committee/cyber

Age-restricted accesses to services while preserving the privacy of individuals

Denis Pinkas
CEO, DP Security Consulting SAS
France

Sector

Cybersecurity

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO/IEC JTC1/SC 27 Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection WG 5 Identity management and privacy technologies

Role

Member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

In several EU countries, legislation has been enacted to protect children and minors. The focus has been placed on preventing access to websites restricted for individuals over 18.

There exist many pieces of legislation, but there needs to be a technical standard that can be followed to know how to implement the requirements that have been enacted.

The work has been initiated two years ago within ISO JTC 1 SC 27 by the BSI (British Standardisation Institution) and by two individuals from two UK organisations who both have been supported by previous StandICT.eu fellowships:

- ▷ Tony Allen (Age Check Certification Scheme - ACCS)
- ▷ Iain Corby (Age Verification Providers Association - AVPA)

The title of this project is: Age Assurance Systems.

Currently, in the UK, age estimation methods are already used and are based on a facial analysis of the individual (not to be confused with facial recognition). These methods use AI (Artificial Intelligence). An intermediary is used to estimate whether an individual is over 18. That intermediary can then charge the web server that will be accessed. The web server cannot authenticate the individual or obtain a face picture. However, the intermediary is in a position to track all the accesses made by individuals.

This method is subject to various types of fraud and in particular, to collaborative attacks between individuals against a web server: for a minor, it is sufficient to present at the right moment the face of an adult that may be close by and who accepts to collaborate.

More robust methods are needed. They need to address the following objectives:

- ▷ the privacy of the individual,
- ▷ the binding of an age-related information to the right individual,
- ▷ the accuracy of the age-related information.

The use of digital identity wallets is foreseen to be the best appropriate solution to support an age verification method, which uses the date of birth of the individual without disclosing it.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

This activity takes a lot of time because it is necessary to prepare a DoC (Disposition of Comments) once a vote has been closed on a document and then a revised document based on this DoC. The Editor and the co-editors do this work.

I am also in a pole position to prepare expert comments on a WD (Working Draft), and comments for a National Body position on a CD (Committee Draft) or on a DIS (Draft International Standard).

Initially, the ISO 27566 project included one part: "The Framework" (ISO 27566-1).

Then after, in October 2023, a second Part was added: "Benchmarks for benchmarking analysis" (ISO 27566-2). In March 2024, as it was anticipated that a vote on an additional Part called "Technical approaches and guidance for implementation" would pass, it was renamed ISO/27566-3.

Unfortunately, this Part (27566-2) failed to meet the JTC 1 rules: only four experts were nominated by NBs, whereas five experts were necessary.

The current situation looks odd as ISO 27566-1 and ISO 27566-3 are present on the ISO web site, but ISO 27566-2 is missing.

I am also involved in the OAuth WG from the IETF. A working draft currently developed within the IETF OAUTH WG is referenced in the ARF 1.4.1 (Architecture Reference Architecture) of the EUDI wallet: Selective Disclosure for JWTs (SD-JWT).

It is available at: draft-ietf-oauth-selective-disclosure-jwt

The current draft does not support the unlinkability principle which is required by Article 5a (16) b from REGULATION (EU) 2024/1183 of 11 April 2024, but which is ignored in the ARF 1.4.1.

I have identified another major problem: the described protocol is insecure.

When a SD-JWT does not contain a set of claims that allows it to identify the End-User, collaborative attacks between End-Users against a Verifier cannot be detected by the Verifier.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

If successful, the impact will not be restricted to European SMEs and/or European societies.

As my contributions are both for ISO and the IETF, the impact can be worldwide. However, I have not observed the presence of another European expert motivated by the topic of Age assurance systems that participates both in ISO JTC1 SC 27 and in the IETF.

Impact on Society

The societal impacts can be important. Age assurance which entails age verification, age estimation and age inference is applicable for a large variety of use cases. Protection of children is the most prominent use case.

There is the need to prevent them from accessing web sites reserved for adults and to control if they have the required age to access social networks. There is also the need to protect them from predators that would not be in the same age range. As an example, a social network for teenagers should control that the users are between 15 and 25. Currently there is a lack of methods and guidance allowing to make these controls correctly.

The most important use case is online when using the Internet. However, controls performed using a digital identity wallet in an online mode can also be done in a proximity mode (NFC). The proximity mode can be used for vending machines or for control in physical accesses to spaces or venues in the presence of a custodian.

At a first glance, the EUDIW (EU Digital identity Wallet) would seem to be appropriate, but it should be observed that it cannot be used world-wide. As an example, a NZ web site that would like to enforce age verification will not be able to use the EUDIW from a EU resident or citizen, as the NZ web site is not established/registered in the EU.

As another example, a US social network that would like to enforce age verification will not be able to use the EUDIW from a EU resident or citizen as the US social network is not established/registered in the EU.

As another example, a US resident or citizen that would like to access a European web site that would like to enforce age verification will not be able to use the EUDIW because he is not a EU citizen.

All these limitations are not technical but come from the EU Regulation. Unless the EU Regulation is changed, these limitations will continue.

The goal of this project which is done at the ISO level is to override these limitations while respecting the privacy of the individuals. The same techniques can be used in other areas like rebates for senior citizens, e.g. over 60 or 65.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

I contributed to developing a new standard series about "Age Assurance Systems" (ISO 27566).

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

I contribute significantly to commenting on the addressed series of new standards.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

Part 1 of ISO 27566 will be shortly under voting at the NB level as a DIS (Draft International Standard). After the failure to launch the Part 2 of ISO 27566, a PWI (Preliminary Work Item) has been opened to continue the discussion on this Part (PWI 27566-2). The future of Part 3 of ISO 27566 is unclear for the moment.

Online references related to the fellowship work

<https://www.iso.org/standard/88147.html>

<https://genorma.com/en/standards/iso-iec-pwi-27566-2>

<https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-ietf-oauth-selective-disclosure-jwt/>
<https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-ietf-oauth-status-list/>

■ Progressing ISO/IEC 29128 parts 2 and 3

Daniel Waszkiewicz

Cryptography specialist, National Institute of Telecommunications

Poland

Sector

Cybersecurity

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27/WG 3 “Security evaluation, testing and specification”

Role

Co-Editor of the working drafts for ISO/IEC 29128-2, “Verification of Cryptographic Protocols - Part 2: Evaluation Methods and Activities for Cryptographic Protocols,” and ISO/IEC 29128-3, “Verification of Cryptographic Protocols - Part 3: Evaluation Methods and Activities for Protocol Implementation Verification.

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

With this fellowship, a primary gap I am addressing is the need for formal verification processes for cryptographic protocols. Although formal verification has been effectively applied in developing protocols such as TLS 1.3 and MLS, there is currently no document standardising this approach. The ISO/IEC 29128-2 standard aims to bridge this gap by offering a systematic framework for formally verifying cryptographic protocol specifications.

In addition to verifying protocol specifications, a significant challenge lies in assessing the implementation of these protocols, especially when it comes to mitigating vulnerabilities caused by programming errors. Incidents like Heartbleed and attacks such as Sweet32 underscore the risks posed by flaws in protocol implementation, even when the underlying cryptographic algorithms are secure. The ISO/IEC 29128-3 standard addresses this concern by providing a framework to identify and address threats stemming from implementation weaknesses in cryptographic protocols.

Moreover, this fellowship supports the objectives of the Cybersecurity Act (CSA) by contributing to the advancement of certification frameworks, including the forthcoming European Cybersecurity Certification scheme. Through these contributions, I am helping to build a more secure and resilient digital infrastructure across Europe.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

This fellowship plays a vital role in enhancing the ICT Standards landscape by tackling the necessity for updated verification standards for cryptographic protocols, especially in alignment with the Cybersecurity Act (CSA). The European Cybersecurity Certification (EUCC) scheme has already identified the outdated ISO/IEC 29128:2011 standard, which has since been retired, emphasising the pressing need to develop the new ISO/IEC 29128-2 and ISO/IEC 29128-3 standards. ISO/IEC 29128-2 aims to establish a comprehensive framework for the formal verification of cryptographic protocol specifications, whereas ISO/IEC 29128-3 focuses on the essential verification of protocol implementations. These initiatives are crucial in advancing the CSA’s objective of building a secure and resilient digital ecosystem throughout Europe.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

A standardized approach to verifying cryptographic protocols within cybersecurity certification schemes has the potential to greatly reduce both the costs and effort involved in certifying complex products and services. By implementing rigorous, standardized verification methods, the overall efficiency of the certification process would improve. This would, to some extent, lower financial entry barriers for SMEs in the certification market, as consistent and dependable protocol verification would simplify the certification of more intricate systems.

Impact on Society

In the broader European context, my fellowship is poised to have a significant impact on cybersecurity practices, aligning with the objectives set forth by the Cybersecurity Act (CSA) and advancing European interests in bolstering digital security.

Adopted in 2019, the Cybersecurity Act represents a pivotal EU regulation aimed at enhancing cybersecurity measures and fostering a secure digital environment. As part of the broader 'single digital market' goal, the CSA streamlines certification procedures, enabling the use of certification as a potent cybersecurity measure without imposing undue burdens on Member States. Previously, products and services underwent certification processes in individual countries, leading to duplicative efforts and inefficiencies. However, with the implementation of the CSA and the forthcoming European Cybersecurity Certification scheme, such duplicative processes will be eliminated. The first European Cybersecurity Certification scheme, compliant with Common Criteria (EUC), is set to be fully operational by February 27th, 2025. This harmonisation ensures that certificates issued under EUC will be legally recognized in every Member State, fostering trust and interoperability across borders.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, my project is directly involved in the development of two new standards, ISO/IEC 29128-2 and ISO/IEC 29128-3, which are intended to replace the earlier version, ISO/IEC 29128:2011. These updated standards will address both the formal verification of cryptographic protocol specifications and the verification of protocol implementations, filling critical gaps left by the previous version.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, as the co-editor, I contribute to the working drafts of ISO 29128 parts 2 and 3 and manage their disposition of comments.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

We successfully developed two DoC documents approved by WG 3 and achieved the next phase in the standardisation process by advancing to the Committee Drafts (CDs) stage instead of the initially planned 3rd Working Drafts. This progress indicates that our efforts so far have been successful. Currently, together with my co-editor, I am working on the CD versions, incorporating feedback collected from experts.

Online references related to the fellowship work

<https://www.iso.org/standard/85850.html>

<https://www.iso.org/committee/45306.html>

Enhancing and Evolving Adaptive Context-Based Access Management for Critical Infrastructure

Samia Oukemeni

*Enterprise Security Architect, Vodafone
Germany*

Sector

Cybersecurity

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ETSI TC-INT AFI (Autonomic Future Internet)
IEEE INGR Security: INGR -International Network Generations
Roadmap”

Role

Member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

My fellowship tackles several gaps in critical infrastructure; firstly, traditional access control systems fail to adapt dynamically to evolving cybersecurity threats and lack advanced mechanisms for real-time decision-making. Also, the existing systems do not sufficiently leverage data-driven insights and analytics for intelligent, context-aware security responses. The current access technologies lack seamless and unified mechanisms for smooth transitions during authentication, especially in the 5G ecosystem. Finally, the access control solutions are fragmented across platforms and technologies, with no standardized framework ensuring consistency and interoperability.

Hence, the priorities of this fellowship are to

- ▷ Develop Real-Time Decision-Making Capabilities: Refine the Control Plane to ensure precise, contextually relevant, and adaptive decision-making in response to security threats.
- ▷ Expand the Knowledge Plane to incorporate data-driven insights and behavioural analysis, enabling modular Zero Trust Architecture (ZTA) solutions tailored for critical infrastructure.
- ▷ Focus on Modular Scalability: Develop scalable solutions that integrate seamlessly with existing systems while supporting rigorous verification and necessity-based access controls.
- ▷ Standardize Access Control Frameworks: Create a unified ACaaS model to address interoperability challenges and provide consistent security policies across platforms.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

My work is based on IETF RFC 2903, ITU-T X.812, and ETSI INT(24)058013 (Adaptive Context-Based Access Management Standardisation and PoC Requirements for Critical Infrastructure). Additional contributions will be made to ETSI INT(24)058013.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

This fellowship project significantly impacts European SMEs and societies by enhancing

cybersecurity in critical infrastructures through the standardisation of ACaaS. By integrating ZTA, the project allows for more secure, scalable, and flexible access control mechanisms, which are crucial for the protection of sensitive data and systems against evolving cyber threats. This approach reduces potential data breaches and security incidents, promoting a safer digital environment.

Impact on Society

My project aligns with the EU's ICT Rolling Plan, emphasising the enhancement of cybersecurity and the development of a resilient, secure digital infrastructure. By focusing on advanced AC techniques rooted in ZTA, the project supports the EU's commitment to integrating ZTA principles into critical infrastructure. Moreover, the project's use of emerging standards and technologies, such as 5G and Beyond, complements the EU's strategy to drive innovation and accelerate digital transformation.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I contribute to new standards. My work titled: " Adaptive Context-Based Access Management Standardisation and PoC Requirements for Critical Infrastructure " is depicted in the ETSI TR (pre-standardisation) document ETSI INT(24)058013 and serves as a foundation for specifications for ACaaS in critical infrastructure, that would eventually turn into a mature standard in the subsequent steps.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, as mentioned above, I am contributing to the technical report at ETSI.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

My contribution to the project is actively progressing, centered around aligning with its focus on refining the Control Plane and expanding the Knowledge Plane. Thus far, I have been engaged in input collection and requirements analysis. These efforts have allowed me to identify gaps, opportunities, and best practices while ensuring alignment with the objectives of stakeholders and SDOs.

Currently, I am synthesising these findings to inform the design of adaptive, analytics-driven access control strategies. This work directly supports the project's goal of enabling real-time decision-making and intelligent security enhancements, setting the foundation for developing a more resilient and scalable AC framework in subsequent phases.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://www.etsi.org/committee/int>

Standards for Information security management, cloud service providers, and digital twins

Karim Tobich

*Consultant, CyberSecurity & Technology Consultancy Ltd
United Kingdom*

Sector

Cybersecurity

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO/IEC JTC1/SC27/WG1 Information security management systems
ISO/IEC JTC1/SC27/WG5 Identity management and privacy technologies

Role

Member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

My fellowship addresses gaps that are related to the development of international standards to help organisations achieve better security and in particular for cloud services providers and cloud service customers. Moreover, this fellowship is intended to provide awareness and potential guidance to privacy concerns related to Digital Twins and their use.

The priority was set and limited to five major standards:

- ▶ ISO/IEC 27003 - Guidance on ISO/IEC 27001;
- ▶ ISO/IEC 27028 - Guidance on ISO/IEC 27002 attributes;
- ▶ ISO/IEC 27017 - Information security controls based on ISO/IEC 27002 for cloud services;
- ▶ ISO/IEC 27658 (PWI) - Security and privacy of digital twins;
- ▶ ISO/IEC TR 27016 - Organisational economics.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

The funding provided the allocation of resources, to perform a well defined ISO/IEC iterative process to create those standards. This includes:

- ▶ Editorial preparation work
- ▶ Editors' meetings
- ▶ Preparation of Call for Contribution (CfC)
- ▶ Experts' contributions
- ▶ Draft Disposition of Comments (DoC) for CfC
- ▶ Editors' meetings for DoC
- ▶ Management meeting (Convenors & editors)
- ▶ Experts' meetings for draft DoC
- ▶ Editors' meetings
- ▶ Preparation of final DoC

The process is repeated from one stage to another until reaching publication. Usually the stages are as follows: PWI, NP, WD1, WD2, WD3, CD1, CD2, DIS, FDIS, and Publication.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

Organisations willing to achieve a resilient cybersecurity system will have to implement an information security management system. The standards developed through this contribution will provide SME and European societies with a comprehensive guidance on how to use ISO/IEC 27001 and ISO/IEC 27002.

Moreover, ISO/IEC 27017 will provide SMEs working as Cloud service providers with a comprehensive list of guidelines to implement when providing services to Cloud service customers.

Impact on Society

Developing and providing such standards to organisations allow them to implement the EU values and policies in an easy manner. More precisely, ISO/IEC 27003, ISO/IEC 27028, and ISO/IEC 27016, are technology agnostic and meant to provide guidance for the implementation and improvement of the governance, risk management and compliances for any organisation. The work on ISO/IEC 27003, and ISO/IEC 27016 fall under the systematic revision cycle to improve those standards, while ISO/IEC 27028 is bringing the notion of custom attributes to make security and cybersecurity controls more flexible and help the adoption of the ISO/IEC 27001 and ISO/IEC 27002 by a wider number of organisations. When it comes to ISO/IEC 27568 and ISO/IEC 27017, those are more technology specific standards and meant to provide Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection to the implementer and user of those technologies.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

The project was used to lead the revision and development of different standards. More precisely, two standards ISO/IEC 27017 and ISO/IEC 27003 benefited indirectly from this fellowship. Those were published respectively, in 2015 and 2017 and were in need for a revision. In addition, this fellowship was used to contribute to the development of a new standard ISO/IEC 27028 to help organisations create their own attributes. Finally, we aim by the end of this fellowship to have recommendations and proposals for developing new standards when it comes to privacy and digital twins.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, I draft essentially Disposition of Comments for the concerned standard revisions.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

Usually, standards get developed in a 36 month cycle period. So far we have received funds for 6 months of work, and we continue the efforts beyond this fellowship period with the aim to obtain more financial support.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 www.iso.org/committee/45306.html

Interoperable configuration and security attestation of Confidential Computing workloads

Nicolae Paladi

CEO CanaryBit.eu

Affiliated researcher, Lund University

Sweden

Sector

Cybersecurity

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) - Remote ATtestation procedureS (RATS) WG

Role

Member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

Through my fellowship I am impacting the following priorities on the call: Innovation for the Digital Single Market for Card, internet and mobile payments, Security in 5G, Cloud computing and IoT, and finally Cybersecurity and Network and Information Security.

This broad impact is primarily explained by the widespread deployment of Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs).

Applications running in TEEs deployed on mobile devices are leveraged to improve security in payments, 5G communication and IoT; for example, by enabling secure communication between IoT devices and secure applications in mobile devices. Secure applications deployed in TEEs on server platforms are leveraged to improve the security of cloud computing and 5G networks.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

Through this fellowship, I am contributing to shape the standards around next-generation secure computing infrastructure. We are on the verge of a new paradigm where the security of the computing infrastructure is endorsed by hardware features and ensures protection of data at rest, in transit, and in use. I am particularly dealing with the standards in the Internet Engineering Task Force, and specifically in the Trusted Execution Environments Platform WG and Remote ATtestation procedureS work group.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

Trusted execution environments (TEEs) allow deploying code and data in a separate, secure segment of computing platforms. Standardised security assessment and provisioning of configuration and personalisation information to Trusted execution environments (TEEs) can be a key contributor to more secure services and an enabler for new products and services. From a European perspective, standardised interoperability of TEE attestation, configuration

and personalisation information will help create secure services throughout the Digital Single Market, enable secure mobile payments, and contribute to more efficient and secure mobile infrastructure for 5G networks, Internet of Things and Cloud Computing.

This fellowship supports my efforts to standardise a common interoperable format for security assessment results and device configuration and personalisation, that will prevent vendor lock-in and will stimulate digital sovereignty and federated interoperability.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

I am contributing to the following RFC developed within the IETF RATS work group: Attestation Results for Secure Interactions.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

I contribute to reviewing the IETF RATS WG Document on Attestation Results for Secure Interactions³.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

Interoperable attestation results for Trusted Execution Environments aim to complement this work by providing a unified information model for attestation results that will be mutually interoperable and acceptable between TEEs and adjacent actors in the confidential computing ecosystem.

Interoperable configuration and personalisation of workloads in Trusted Execution Environments over the network will enable broad adoption and deployment of confidential computing in network, edge and cloud infrastructure. This activity represents an essential and logical next step for successfully deploying confidential computing applications on commodity platforms.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-ietf-rats-ar4si/>

³ <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/html/draft-ietf-rats-ar4si>

Advance Biometric System-onCard standard series

Robert Mueller

*Independent expert, Dr. Robert Mueller IT Consulting
Germany*

Sector

Cybersecurity

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO/IEC SC17 WG11 Cards and security devices for personal identification

Role

Editor of two standards and technical expert contributor

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

Technology for Biometric System-on-Card (BSoC) has advanced significantly since the first publication of the ISO/IEC 17839 series from 2014-2016. This made an amendment of part 2 necessary in 2021 and a revision started 2022/2023. Major gaps are that the currently published standards partially refer to outdated technology and do not cover many recent industry developments in the field of BSoC. This includes enrolment methodologies, sensor and card manufacturing, but also processes and usage of biometric cards. The priority is to consider all inputs from national bodies, come to a consensus and progress the standard series according to the ISO business plan. Challenges are diverse inputs from industry delegates targeting different solutions. This may lead to another part in the ISO/IEC 17839 series.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

This fellowship covers the multi-part standard ISO/IEC 17839 Biometric System-on-Card. A BSoC is a smart card that includes an entire biometric verification system with capture device, signal processing, storage, comparison and decision/action. Part 1 specifies core requirements including the architecture of a BSoC and types. Part 2 covers physical characteristics for all formats and part 3 is responsible for logical information interchange with the outside world of a BSoC. The standard is referenced by multiple applications including payment scheme specifications by Mastercard and Visa. Other applications include government ID, access control and transport. The initiation of a revision of the standard was due to the regular ISO cycle period and due to liaison input requests from applications mentioned above. While part 2 has already been advanced to DIS status with a previous StandICT.eu funded fellowship project, parts 1 and 3 are currently in CD stage and will be advanced to DIS and CD2, respectively.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

The standard promotes Biometric System-on-Card architecture, characteristics and interfaces. It is a technology that improves security and privacy for citizens in Europe and beyond, because personal data remains on a personal card. The interoperability achieved

with this standard helps particularly SMEs who typically provide only a single component to a BSoC while larger corporations could provide an entire solution which may be proprietary.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I am contributing to the revision of the multi-part standard ISO/IEC 17839 Biometric System-on-Cardparts 1 and 3, which are currently in CD stage and will be advanced to DIS and CD2, respectively.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, I contribute to drafting the revised standard documents for the ISO/IEC 17839-1 and -3 revision.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

Working group meetings for SC17 WG11 took place in Sydney, 2024-10-14 to 2024-10-16 and 2024-12-09 to 2024-12-11. The fellow in the role of the editor prepared proposed dispositions of comments before the meeting which were discussed and advanced to an approved disposition, respectively. ISO/IEC 17839-1 was promoted to DIS stage while ISO/IEC 17839-3 remained in CD stage. More input was received and integrated as new text contributions to the document. A new commenting cycle has been launched and the editor will prepare another proposed disposition of comments in the next months. The next working group meetings are scheduled for May and September 2025.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 www.iso.org/committee/45144.html

AI & Cybersecurity Standards in Education II (Project Continuation)

Sandra Feliciano

Founder and CEO, AESTAS INSIGNIS - Investigação e Suportes de Apoio à Gestão, Unipessoal, Lda.

Portugal

Sector

Cybersecurity

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

IPQ/CT 187 Formal, non-formal and informal learning
ISO/TC 232 Education and Learning Services
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27 Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42 Artificial Intelligence
IPQ/CT 163 Security in Information Systems
IPQ/CT 223 Artificial Intelligence

Role

Chair of IPQ/CT 187 Formal, non-formal and informal learning

Head of Delegation at ISO/TC 232 Education and Learning Services

Liaison Officer between ISO/TC 232 and ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27 Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection

Liaison Officer between ISO/TC 232 and ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42 Artificial Intelligence

Delegate at IPQ/CT 163 Security in Information Systems

Delegate at IPQ/CT 223 Artificial Intelligence

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

This fellowship project is a continuation of a previous one funded under the StandICT.eu 3rd call. Therefore, the addressed gaps and priorities remain the same as in the previous activity, including namely:

- ▶ “Standardisation Gap in AI Implementation: There is a lack of standardized guidelines for implementing AI in educational settings. This project aims to fill this gap by developing guidelines that ensure a harmonized approach across countries.
- ▶ Cybersecurity Risks in Education: Educational institutions are increasingly becoming targets of cyber threats. This project addresses the challenge of safeguarding sensitive educational data and ensuring the privacy and security of students and staff in the digital environment.
- ▶ Educator Preparedness: As per Rose Luckin’s insights, there is a significant gap in educators’ confidence in understanding and safeguarding against AI threats. This project aims to equip educators with the necessary skills and knowledge to confidently use AI tools in a secure manner.
- ▶ Ethical Use of AI: The project addresses the challenge of ensuring ethical AI usage in education, focusing on issues like transparency, accountability, and bias. This is crucial in

maintaining trust in AI technologies among educators, students, and parents.

- ▷ Diverse Educational Landscapes: Europe's diverse educational landscape presents a challenge in implementing a one-size-fits-all approach. This project aims to develop flexible guidelines that can be adapted to different educational systems and cultural contexts within Europe.
- ▷ Keeping Pace with Technological Advancements: AI is a rapidly evolving field. The project addresses the challenge of keeping educational standards up-to-date with these advancements, ensuring that educators and students are prepared for the future."

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

As a follow-up activity to my previous fellowship (OC#3), I continued developing two new standardisation documents, namely two new ISO International Workshop Agreements (IWA) with guidelines on how to implement

- ▷ ISO 27001 - Information security management system - requirements
- ▷ and ISO 42001 - Artificial intelligence management system - requirements in educational organisations.

It therefore contributes to the ICT Standards landscape by, on one hand, adding two IWA to the ISO catalogue and, on the other, contributing to market adoption of both ISO 27001 and ISO 42001 by providing sector-specific guidelines.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on Society

It impacts educational organisations in any country and of all legal forms and sizes (including SME) and also includes training departments of SMEs from other economic sectors. Moreover, by tailoring ISO 42001 and ISO 27001 to the education sector, the project directly strengthens the cybersecurity posture of educational institutions across Europe. This includes safeguarding sensitive student data and protecting educational infrastructures from cyber threats. Also, the development of specific guidelines ensures a harmonized approach to cybersecurity across European educational systems, fostering a more secure and resilient digital education environment.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I am developing pre-normative work; new work item proposals for two new full Guidance Standards.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, I contribute to drafting two new work item proposals for guidelines on how to implement ISO 27001 and ISO 42001 in educational organisations.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

This project is a continuation of a previous fellowship, which outputs were the engagement of a community of Experts and a formal proposal for the establishment of an ISO Workshop to develop two International Workshop Agreements (IWA) submitted to IPQ and ISO for approval. During this new project timeline, this proposal was analysed and rejected by both NSBs for the below two different reasons:

- ▷ IPQ's position is that these two guidelines should be developed as full standards and not IWAs;

- ▷ ISO refuses to proceed with the IWA Ballot among ISO Members without the support of IPQ, for a matter of principle - even if the ISO Directives allow it.

Therefore, the guidelines are now being developed as pre-normative work, using the expertise of the community of Experts previously engaged and the resulting documents will be submitted to IPQ and ISO, as new work item proposals for two new full Guidance Standards instead of IWAs.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://www.iso.org/committee/537864.html>

 <https://www.iso.org/committee/6794475.html>

Strengthening security and privacy of biometrics applications through standards

Julien Bringer

CEO, Kallistech

France

Sector

E-privacy

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27 Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection /WG 5 Identity management and privacy technologies
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27/WG 3 Security evaluation, testing and specification

ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 37 Biometrics /WG 5

ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 37/WG 3

ISO/IEC 24745

CEN/ CENELEC JTC 13 Cybersecurity and data protection WG5

Role

Member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

With this fellowship, I am addressing gaps in privacy protection, cybersecurity, identity protection, and applications of biometric technologies: leading and contributing to on-going projects in ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27 and SC 37 related to biometrics authentication and identification to enforce highest security and privacy requirements to protect end-users following the core principles of EU personal data protection regulation, and even beyond by enforcing security and privacy by *technical* design. ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC27 had published a standard late 2022 27553-1 on security and privacy requirements for biometrics authentication towards remote services when biometrics information remains on a mobile device. However, there are many deployed solutions for which some biometrics information is sent remotely, without clear guidelines or requirements, thus leading to huge risks for end-users. SC27 has thus also initiated a project 27553-2 for the cases where some info is sent to remote services; this project reaches its final step (DIS stage). It is critical to support this project for finalising it with a strong focus on privacy and security by technical design and to enforce the highest practices for a better protection of end-users. The activity leads the final steps toward publication (aiming for publication before the end of 2025) for this project, ideally by reaching FDIS after the next (on-going) round of comments on the 1st DIS.

In parallel with 27553-2, there are other biometrics-related standards in development, leveraging biometrics (and other personal information) for identification or for authentication, with security and privacy challenges. Notably, with this activity we should be able to reach the publication of 27553-2 and 19792, and thus setting strong roots for future secure and private by design biometrics applications.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

The master goal of this fellowship is to ensure security and privacy of sensitive data (of biometrics) are more and more (and better than today) taken in account, to ensure consistency

FOLLOWING THE FELLOWS / IMPACT REPORT FROM FUNDED APPLICANTS TO THE STANDICT.EU 2026 FELLOWSHIP PROGRAMME / FIFTH OPEN CALL

with the highest standards (from the transversal standard 24745 developed in ISO/IEC JTC1/SC27 Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection), and also considering the recent progresses in privacy enhancing technologies. This will enable it to be aligned with the high requirements from the EU market, at least, and even to reach additional protection by technical design.

The activity led to the development of the final phases of ISO/IEC 27553-2 and ISO/IEC 19792. In addition, the activity includes other on-going or anticipated projects leveraging biometrics (and other personal information) for identification or for authentication, as ISO/IEC DIS 9868, and the recently launched revision of ISO/IEC 19989-1.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

Toward the development of EU-friendly solutions for biometrics-based services, employing strong privacy enhancing technologies, thus going further contractual/organisational requirements, to ensure privacy and security by design. Promoting the use of the newest privacy enhancing technologies is in particular very important (biometric technologies are more and more seen as a way to fight against authentication/identification threats in our digital lives) as sharing or leaking biometric information without appropriate protection can be very critical. This supports innovation in the EU market and a common approach between the member states. And it helps the EU providers to be ahead of the competitors internationally. Similarly for security evaluation, alignment/consistency and to take in account latest threats is required. This impacts the EU solution providers / vendors and capability to ensure the appropriate level of security and privacy protection in the EU.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I contribute to both revising existing standards and developing new ones; 27553-2 is new. 19792 is a revision. 19989 has been recently launched as a revision. And potential new proposals to come in order to complement 27553-2.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, I have contributed to the technical reports.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

Once the dispositions of comments for these different standardisation projects have been made, during the first part of 2025 I am participating in their respective resolution meetings aiming to prepare the next working drafts of these standards. The work is still in progress and will continue beyond this fellowship duration.

Online references related to the fellowship work

<https://www.iso.org/committee/45306.html>

https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:7:0:::FSP_ORG_ID:2307986&cs=1BFE244DDA2A68D1B5C93795034A8DD05

2. Key enablers and security

The background is a vibrant digital landscape. It features a central fingerprint scan rendered in glowing blue and white dots. Surrounding the fingerprint are various digital motifs: binary code (0s and 1s) scattered throughout, glowing blue and green circuit-like lines, and several concentric, glowing blue rings that create a sense of depth and motion. The overall color palette is dominated by deep blues, bright cyan, and vibrant greens, giving it a high-tech, cybernetic feel.

■ RXQ - rLEDBAT for Quic

Marcelo Bagnulo

Associate Professor Universidad Carlos III de Madrid
Spain

Sector

5G & beyond 6G

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

| Internet Congestion Control RG (ICCRG)

Role

Member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

A critical research challenge addressed by 6G technology is the provision of “Extreme Experience,” which encompasses ultra-high bitrates and exceptionally low latencies. Queuing delay is one of the major latency sources in Internet communications and 6G must drastically reduce it to achieve extremely low latencies. Queuing delay is determined by the interaction between the Transport protocol used by the host (notably the Congestion Control Algorithm (CCA)) and the bottleneck buffer of the network.

Over the last few years, we have witnessed a refreshing spring in Transport protocol research, resulting in a number of innovations that aim to reduce latency and are starting to get traction in the Internet and are capable of contributing towards the latency reduction envisioned for 6G. Notable examples of these technologies are QUIC, LEDBAT++ and rLEDBAT.

While all these three technologies contribute to reducing the latency experienced by applications, currently, there are pieces missing to enable fully seizing the benefits these technologies can provide. In particular, we identify the following gaps in the standardisation:

- ▶ the standardisation of rLEDBAT for TCP is yet not completed.
- ▶ the standardisation of LEDBAT++ is not yet completed neither
- ▶ rLEDBAT for QUIC has not been described, much less standardized.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

With this fellowship, I am to help complete the standardisation of rLEDBAT in the Internet Congestion Control Research Group (ICCRG) in the IETF/IRTF and of LEDBAT++ in the ICCRG in the IETF. I also support the definition of the mechanisms to allow rLEDBAT support in a QUIC receiver, enabling the QUIC protocol to benefit from the performance gains resulting from rLEDBAT. I also produce a specification of the rLEDBAT extensions for the QUIC protocol in the form of an Internet draft that will be submitted for discussion in the ICCRG

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on Society

This activity contributes to achieving 6G’s vision. To achieve low latency, 6G will have to embrace the novel Transport protocols that are being adopted in the Internet, notably Quic/BBR, LEDBAT++/rLEDBAT, as they are designed to reduce the latency of the communications.

The RXQ project work on the integration of QUIC and rLEDBAT will provide one key missing piece in the toolset to achieve low latency.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I contribute to three Internet drafts of new standardisation items, including:

- ▶ the rLEDBAT specification⁴
- ▶ the LEDBAT++ specification⁵
- ▶ the specification of rLEDBAT for QUIC.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, I contribute to the above mentioned technical specifications.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The work on these three Internet drafts is processing: .

- ▶ The rLEDBAT specification is in the latest stages of the process and hopefully will be published soon, we are helping in these last steps.
- ▶ The LEDBAT++ specification still needs a bit of work. We have agreed with the ICCRG chairs and the LEDBAT++ authors that I will be the editor of the specification, leading the remaining parts of the process.
- ▶ The specification of rLEDBAT for QUIC: we expect to produce an initial version of the specification by April 2025.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-irtf-iccrq-rledbat/>

 <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-irtf-iccrq-ledbat-plus-plus/>

4 <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-irtf-iccrq-rledbat/>

5 <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-irtf-iccrq-ledbat-plus-plus/>

Enhancing EN AI Risk Management with Fundamental Rights and Children's Protection

Alessio Tartaro

*PhD researcher, University of Sassari
Italy*

Sector

Artificial intelligence

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

CEN/CENELEC/JTC21 AI/WG2 - Operational aspects

Role

Member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

CEN-CENELEC JTC21 is currently developing a harmonized standard on AI risk management to support the operationalisation of the risk management requirements of Article 9 of the AI Act. When the standard meets the requirements of the AI Act and is referenced in the Official Journal of the European Union, this standard can be used by AI providers to achieve a presumption of conformity with the AI Act's AI risk management requirements, facilitating market entry and building trust. Contributing to this standard is therefore a priority, as it will serve to implement and achieve the goals of the AI Act.

Article 9(9) of the AI Act requires, among other things, that special consideration be given to the potential adverse effects of the AI Act on persons under the age of 18. For this reason, specific measures to identify and mitigate risks of AI systems to persons under the age of 18, i.e. children as defined by the UNCRC, should be included in the standard. Otherwise, there is a risk that the standard will not comply with the requirements of the AI Act and therefore cannot be used for presumption of conformity with respect to Article 9(9).

In its current state, however, the standard does not contain specific provisions for the protection of children's rights. My contribution aims to fill this gap.

Two main challenges can be identified when developing and including specific measures to protect children's rights from AI risks in the standard. First, the topic is new to technical standardisation and there are few documents relevant to the topic. Second, the current stage of development of the project in CEN-CENELEC JTC21 is such that the topic has not been able to receive the attention it deserves, as more fundamental questions about the structure and scope of the standard are still being discussed.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

In the framework of this fellowship, I am contributing to the development of a standard for AI risk management in CEN-CENELEC JTC21. This project significantly contributes to the ICT Standards landscape by expanding the scope of risk management in the field of AI. Risk management is a fundamental practice in the ICT sector, as it enables minimising real risks and building trust. With the entry into force of the AI Act, risk management for AI systems

becomes even more critical. In fact, Article 9 of the Regulation states that a risk management system must be implemented for high-risk AI systems throughout the entire AI system lifecycle. Although standards such as ISO/IEC 23894 consider this issue, they are not aligned with the AI Act. Therefore, a European standard is needed.

My contribution aims to expand the scope of this standard with specific measures to protect children's rights, as required by the AI Act. This can be achieved by drawing on existing standards for the protection of children in digital environments. The most relevant standard in this context is CWA 18016:2023 - Age appropriate digital services framework. I contributed to the EN AI risk management by providing comments to integrate the protection of children's rights into the standard. To this end, I developed proposed requirements inspired by CWA 18016:2023 and tailored to the AI context. Given the current state of development of EN AI Risk Management, the comments have not yet been addressed and a decision has not yet been made whether these comments will be incorporated into the standard.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

This project directly benefits European SMEs operating in the AI sector by streamlining their approach to compliance with the AI Act, particularly concerning the protection of children's rights. Many SMEs may lack the internal expertise or resources to adequately address Article 9(9), leading to potential uncertainties, implementation complexities, and unforeseen costs.

My project addresses this gap head-on. It clarifies compliance requirements, offering a standardized approach that minimizes the risk of costly errors and helps SMEs avoid potential legal and reputational damages. By pre-emptively addressing this complex compliance issue, the project also allows SMEs to focus their resources on innovation and growth, rather than reactive problem-solving. It is a win-win situation where compliance is facilitated and SMEs become more competitive in the European and global markets.

Impact on Society

This project significantly contributes to several societal impacts, aligning with European values and the growing need for responsible and trustworthy AI, especially concerning vulnerable populations like children. By incorporating child protection considerations into EN AI risk management, this project directly addresses a crucial gap in current AI development practices.

Specifically, this integration supports the enhancement of child safety and well-being in the digital age. AI systems are increasingly prevalent in areas that affect children (e.g., education, toys, social media). By including child protection within the risk management framework, this project proactively mitigates the potential for harm. It ensures that AI systems are designed and deployed with a focus on safeguarding children's rights and well-being, reducing risks related to privacy breaches, manipulation, inappropriate content exposure, and psychological harm.

This proactive embedding of child protection considerations within a recognized European standard, will lead to the development of AI systems in line with the requirements of the AI Act, in particular Article 9(9) which requires specific consideration for children's rights.

Finally, the project provides AI developers, manufacturers, and deployers with a clear and practical framework for incorporating child protection considerations into their work. This standardisation provides actionable guidelines and tools for systematically assessing and managing potential risks to children, reducing the possibility of unintentional harm arising from the technology itself. By proactively addressing the specific risks AI might pose to children, the project builds trust and confidence in AI systems. This enhanced trust is crucial for the widespread adoption of AI technologies, promoting innovation while ensuring alignment with European values and fundamental rights, in line with the AI Act objectives

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

No, not directly since I aim to expand the scope of the target standard.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

No.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

I reckon that as the comments and contributions presented during the fellowship have not yet been discussed and approved, follow-up action is needed to ensure that EN AI risk management includes explicit requirements and recommendations to ensure adequate protection of children's rights.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:22:0:::FSP_ORG_ID,FSP_LANG_ID:2916257,25&cs=1827B89DA69577BF3631EE2B6070F207D

AI logging and monitoring expert contributions for hEN AI standards

Sabrina Palme
CEO & Co-Founder, Palqee Technologies
United Kingdom

Sector

Artificial intelligence

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42/WG 1 “Foundational standards”
CEN/CLC JTC 21/WG 2 “Operational aspects”
CEN/CLC JTC 21/WG 4 “Foundational and societal aspects”

Role

Member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a key component of the Rolling Plan for ICT standardisation, supporting the European Commission’s Standardisation Request issued to back the AI Act. My contribution is aligned with the objectives of the AI Key Enablers, particularly in the areas of Cybersecurity in AI and the Data Economy.

The development of standards that provide businesses with benchmarks and guidelines for conformity with the EU AI Act is under time pressure. However, this process faces challenges, including a shortage of experts contributing to specific topics covered by the standardisation request and the underrepresentation of important stakeholders, such as startups and SMEs. These factors risk delaying the delivery of necessary standards.

With my contributions and active involvement, the following gaps and challenges are being addressed:

- ▶ Expert Contributions in AI Logging and Monitoring: As an expert in AI Logging and Monitoring, I am actively contributing to the relevant Working Groups and standards. My expertise supports the development of standards that are essential for ensuring AI system compliance and trustworthiness.
- ▶ Representation of Startup Interests: As a startup founder, I bring the perspective of the startup industry into the standardisation process. This ensures that the developed standards are relevant and applicable to smaller companies that are driving innovation in the AI sector.
- ▶ Supporting Timely Delivery of Standards: My contributions, particularly in AI logging and monitoring, are aimed at facilitating the timely delivery of harmonised standards, providing businesses with the guidance they need to comply with the EU AI Act.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

My contributions focus on critical areas such as AI logging, monitoring, and post-market monitoring, which are essential for ensuring compliance with the EU AI Act. I bring specialised knowledge that supports the development of robust and effective standards.

My involvement in both CEN/CENELEC and ISO/IEC Working Groups enhances the alignment

of European standards with international practices, ensuring consistency and interoperability across different regions. This cross-standardisation effort is important for creating standards that are not only compliant with European regulations but also competitive in the global market.

Furthermore, as a startup founder, I provide a practical perspective that ensures the needs of startups and SMEs are adequately considered in the standardisation process. This inclusion is vital for developing standards that are applicable to businesses of all sizes, making the resulting standards more broadly relevant and easier to implement.

Overall, my contributions support the timely development of harmonised standards that meet regulatory requirements and reflect the realities of the AI industry, adding considerable value to the ICT standardisation processes as a whole.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

A key impact of this work is the inclusion of startup and SME perspectives in the standardisation process. As a startup founder, I am committed to ensuring that the standards developed are not only aligned with regulatory requirements but also practical and applicable for smaller businesses. This consideration is essential for creating standards that are relevant across different business sizes and sectors.

In addition, this activity will support the parallel development of AI logging and monitoring standards at both CEN/CLC and ISO/IEC levels. By contributing to these efforts, the activity will help to ensure that European standards are consistent with international developments, promoting alignment and interoperability.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I contribute to defining new standards on AI. As part of my involvement in CEN/CLC JTC21 drafting harmonised AI standards in line with the EU Commission standardisation request following the EU AI Act, one critical area that requires immediate attention is Post-Market Monitoring (PMM) systems, a specific requirement under the EU AI Act. Despite its importance, contributions to this area were noticeably lacking. As a developer of AI monitoring solutions, I have underscored the necessity of addressing PMM in the standards to provide clear, actionable guidance to businesses. This necessity has been recognised and incorporated by CEN/CLC JTC 21/WG 1 - TCF and is now being implemented by WG 2 developing the Quality Management Standard.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, I made especially technical contributions on post-market monitoring, a specific requirement under the EU AI Act.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

With this fellowship, I contribute directly to the timely delivery of harmonised European Standards (hEN) that provide businesses with benchmarks for trustworthy AI and compliance with the EU AI Act. By developing clear standards for post-market monitoring, as well as logging and monitoring, this activity will help meet the regulatory requirements set out under the EU AI Act, ensuring that businesses have practical guidance for compliance.

Online references related to the fellowship work

https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:22:0:::FSP_ORG_ID,FSP_LANG_ID:2916257,25&cs=1827B89DA69577BF3631EE2B6070F207D

Research for potential PAS development: “Guidance for Climate Action with AI”

Alastair Marke

*Director General, Blockchain and Climate Institute
Estonia*

Sector

Artificial intelligence

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO-IEC/JTC 1/SC42/WG4 Use Cases and Applications
ISO-IEC/JTC 1/SC42/JAG Joint Advisory Group on AI and sustainability
with ISO/IEC JTC1/SC 39 and JTC1/SC 42
CEN-CENELEC/JTC21/WG4 Foundational and societal aspects
ISO/TC 307/WG3 Smart Contracts

Role

Member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

My fellowship focuses on researching the feasibility of developing an international (e.g. ISO) standard for deploying Artificial Intelligence (AI) in climate action, culminating in a Technical Report following consultation with chairs of relevant ISO technical committees. The initiative seeks to address key challenges in aligning AI with climate goals, particularly in Least Developed Countries (LDCs), which face barriers such as limited infrastructure, poor data quality and insufficient expertise. The research will explore standardisation opportunities to ensure AI technologies are interoperable, transparent and ethically deployed, furthermore, aligning them with global sustainability and regulatory priorities. Focusing on bridging the digital divide, fostering inclusivity and empowering local stakeholders through capacity-building initiatives, the project will also tackle cybersecurity, privacy concerns and environmental impacts of AI. Moreover, it will have recommendations on energy-efficient and ethical solutions. Taking into consideration integrating AI with key enablers like IoT and Big Data, the research aims to enhance AI-driven climate action while minimising risks. The findings will serve as a foundation for a unified framework, positioning Europe as a global leader in AI standardisation and reinforcing its commitment to sustainable development.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

This funded project contributes to the ICT standards landscape by exploring the development of an ISO Technical Report that serves as a foundation for future standards in deploying Artificial Intelligence (AI) for climate action. The project focuses on creating a unified framework to ensure the responsible, secure and sustainable application of AI in addressing climate challenges, particularly in Least Developed Countries (LDCs). It aligns with the EU's ICT priorities by addressing key areas such as data governance, cybersecurity and ethical AI deployment. The research emphasises interoperability, scalability and transparency, ensuring AI solutions meet the diverse needs of stakeholders and align with international norms.

Key ICT standards addressed include ISO/IEC JTC 1 SC42 (Artificial Intelligence), ISO/IEC 27001 (Information Security), and emerging standards on sustainable digital practices. The

project examines standards for Big Data, IoT, and cloud computing integration, ensuring AI systems are interoperable and privacy-preserving. It also aligns with EU regulations like the AI Act, focusing on ethical frameworks and environmental sustainability. The outcomes will guide ISO committees and stakeholders in defining best practices for AI in climate action, addressing global challenges while reinforcing Europe's leadership in the ICT standards landscape.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on Society

Beyond the immediate focus on AI and climate action, the project is expected to have a wide-ranging impact on several broader European interests:

- ▶ **Promoting Environmental Sustainability:** The standardisation of AI applications will significantly enhance Europe's ability to meet its environmental sustainability goals. AI technologies, when effectively applied, can greatly improve the cost-effectiveness in monitoring, predicting, mitigating and adapting to the impacts of climate change.
- ▶ **Addressing Cybersecurity and E-Privacy Challenges:** The project's comprehensive approach to addressing cybersecurity and e-privacy issues will have a significant impact on building public trust in AI technologies. It will not only protect European citizens but also set a global benchmark for the responsible and secure use of AI in climate action, reinforcing Europe's leadership in digital governance.
- ▶ **Supporting Global Standards and Inclusivity:** While the primary focus is on Europe, the global applicability of the standards developed through this project could have a far-reaching impact. By providing standardised, reliable, and secure AI tools for climate action, the project could also support developing countries, which do not necessarily have such technical capacity, in their efforts to combat climate change. This aligns with the UNFCCC Technology Mechanism's work plan and highlights the project's potential to contribute to global climate resilience efforts.
- ▶ **Advancing the Digital Single Market:** Finally, by standardising AI-driven innovations in areas like E-Government, FinTech and Blockchain, the project will play a crucial role in advancing the Digital Single Market. This will not only drive digital transformation within the EU but also support the transition to a low-carbon economy. This research will potentially also serve major regulations like the EU AI Act, the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR) and the EU's Green Deal. This research aims to provide a solid ground for the development of standards that ensure AI technologies are both effective in climate action and sustainable by design.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Not directly. The outcome, a produced technical report, will guide ISO committees and stakeholders in defining best practices for AI in climate action.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, I have contributed to drafting a technical report.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The Technical Report proposal has been presented to ISO-IEC/JTC1/SC42/JAG (AI in Sustainability) and ISO/TC207/SC7 (Climate Change-related Activities) twice respectively. Some stakeholder engagement sessions have been held. Pending internal discussions of various national delegations, this proposal may be further discussed at the next plenaries.

Promote AI trustworthiness through fundamental rights protections in EU / International AI Standards

Patricia Shaw

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Sector

Artificial intelligence

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

CEN/CENELEC JTC21 AI WG 2 Risk management
CEN/CENELEC JTC21 AI WG 4 Trustworthiness
BSI Art.1 and ISO JTC1/SC42

Role

Member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

My work to date has been seeking to promote trustworthiness through fundamental rights protections in European harmonised technical standards concerning AI, in particular JTC21.

Challenges I have been addressing is in the Working Groups 2 (Risk Management) and Working Groups 4 (Trustworthiness) of JTC21 to build consensus concerning technical and organisation requirements that are both feasible, pragmatic yet meet the requirements of the EU AI Act which are orientated towards the AI provider and horizontal, in that they do not specifically address one particular vertical sector/industry.

Gaps has been to increase understanding of what fundamental rights are, and how different cohorts of affected people can be impacted in real terms by AI systems. This has been necessary to help build standards requirements (both normative and informative) that identify fundamental rights hazards, identify rights holders who might be impacted and affected, to distill what risks need to be evaluated, and seek to mitigate them through risk controls and manage them to an acceptable level of residual risk which is lawful. In Working Group 2, I have been working with other experts to help define a method for fundamental rights due diligence as part of risk management. This has required looking at stakeholder analysis, intended purpose and intended use so that hazards and reasonably foreseeable misuse can also be correctly identified. In Working Group 4, the main bulk of my interventions have been concerning risk mitigations and controls such as human oversight.

Moreover, risk management and human oversight for fundamental rights hazards have been two key priorities that undergird trustworthiness.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

The EU has requested the CEN/CENELEC JTC21 committee to create standards which are fit for harmonisation in accordance with the EU AI Act. Article 1 of the EU AI Act requires AI systems to afford a high level of protection of health, safety and fundamental rights. The standardisation request is a first of its kind to require fundamental rights to be covered

in a technical standard. My work is directly seeking to build European Norms which are harmonizable and that protect fundamental rights in practical terms in the design, development and deployment of High Risk AI systems.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

AI Providers both large and small need to do due diligence in relation to risks to fundamental rights. Assessment of those risks and risk controls will be pertinent to organisations of all sizes. High risk AI systems have the potential to result in impacts at scale, irrespective of the size of the organisation that puts it on the market or puts it into service.

Impact on Society

This activity will contribute to making European and International AI standards that protects against unintended foreseeable risks to equality and fundamental rights and intentionally designs for the enhancement of equality and fundamental rights. Also, it supports increasing understanding and awareness of the impact of AI on affected individuals and groups in respect of their equality and fundamental rights with technology companies, national standards bodies, and notified bodies;

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

My work is directly involved in developing first of its kind technical standards attempting to address fundamental rights hazards brought about through the AI lifecycle in respect of High Risk AI under the EU AI Act. These new “homegrown” EU standards will form part of compliance through a presumption of conformity with the law.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, I have made technical contributions through drafting standards input on fundamental rights risk catalogue, and fundamental rights worked use cases.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The project is on its half-way, and I continue to aid consensus building and drafting of the standards which include essential expertise in the very specific area of fundamental rights which is urgently needed in JTC21 working groups.

Online references related to the fellowship work

https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:22:0:::FSP_ORG_ID,FSP_LANG_ID:2916257,25&cs=1827B89DA69577BF3631EE2B6070F207D

AI-CoE Phase II: Artificial Intelligence for Business powered by Center of Excellence. Model and TS

Javier Peris

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Sector

Artificial intelligence

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

UNE ICT mirror subcommittees for: ISO/IEC JTC 1 (ICT), subcommittees SC40 (ICT Management), WG 7 Centres of Excellence.

Role

Chair of UNE CTN 71/SC 40 "IT Governance and Service Management"

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

In this fellowship, the main priority focuses on helping organisations to drive innovation and technological transformation using the Centre of Excellence (CoE) as the best management mechanism in a context of a shortage of professional profiles with expertise in Artificial Intelligence and other disruptive technologies.

The expansion of artificial intelligence must overcome important gaps such as:

- ▶ The high failure rate in AI initiatives (80% according HBR 2021).
- ▶ The knowledge resides inside specialised vendors and not in the organisations.
- ▶ More importance is given to the technology than to the benefit it brings to the business.
- ▶ It is difficult to reuse experiences in an organisation.
- ▶ There is no standardised way on how to adopt and implement AI-based solutions.

In addition, the application of AI in transforming organisations faces significant challenges. Such as, there are barriers to sharing knowledge across projects and areas in organisations.

Also, successful AI projects have a strong unexpected over-demand for knowledge sharing, which pulls them to failure in the next project. AI projects are scattered and do not follow a common pattern, and therefore each initiative has to reinvent how to work.

The other challenges are related specifically to the center of excellence that I address with this fellowship. The concept of sharing expertise and success stories through a Center of Excellence is unknown and not on the agenda of executives. A poorly structured and managed Center of Excellence can degenerate into bureaucracy, costs, and loss of value.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

I am working on the creation of a new series of standards that facilitates the AI adoption. These new standards on Centres of Excellence (CoE) in AI will enable companies to improve in two key areas: to early expand AI utilisation and to reduce the high risk of failure of AI initiatives. Today, there are no international standards that address how to apply AI successfully across

an organisation's multiple activities. These CoE on AI adoption standards series will be useful specially for small organisations, but also for large corporations.

This new standards in progress are:

- ▶ UNE-71405 "Centres of Excellence to drive Artificial Intelligence and other disruptive change. State of the Art. Technical Report".
- ▶ UNE-71406 "Centres of Excellence to drive Artificial Intelligence and other disruptive change - Implementation Guidelines. Technical Specification".

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

European small organisations do not have the experts or economic resources to hire specialised AI consultants, so they must postpone the application of AI in their businesses. This generates a new delay in their innovation gap. The main opportunity for SMEs is their incorporation to a future sectorial cluster type and other potential movements of knowledge collectivisation.

Creating a standard on how to constitute and manage an AI Center of Excellence enables European small companies to have a higher success rate in AI innovation initiatives, making them easier to realise and reducing risk.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, with this fellowship I am working on the creation of a new series of standards that facilitates the AI adoption via the use of the Centre of Excellence management model in order to centralise and share expertise. This new standards series will be:

- ▶ UNE-71405 "Centres of Excellence to drive Artificial Intelligence and other disruptive change. State of the Art. Technical Report".
- ▶ UNE-71406 "Centres of Excellence to drive Artificial Intelligence and other disruptive change - Implementation Guidelines. Technical Specification".

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, as mentioned in the above, I am working on a technical report and technical specifications.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The initiative is positively following the work plan set out in the planning. The work model and the guidelines to facilitate the creation and management of Centres of Excellence to drive Artificial Intelligence are providing significant insights.

Online references related to the fellowship work

www.une.org/encuentra-tu-norma/comites-tecnicos-de-normalizacion/comite?c=CTN+71/SC+40

Contribution to AI Trustworthiness Framework and AI System Risk Management EN standards for AI Act

Anita Prinzie

*Senior Responsible AI Lead, Datashift
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Sector

Artificial intelligence

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

CEN/CENELEC JTC 21 Artificial Intelligence WG 4 Foundational and societal aspects
WG 2 AI Engineering
WG 1 Strategic Advisory Group

Role

Member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

The AI Act is a European regulation promoting the uptake of human-centric and trustworthy AI, while ensuring protection of health, safety, and fundamental rights. Companies can prove conformity with the AI Act by complying with the 10 harmonized standards drafted by CEN-CENELEC.

The objective of this fellowship is to enable the progression from draft stage (prEN) to approval stage FprEN for two of these harmonized standards supporting the implementation of the AI Act:

- ▷ EN AI Trustworthiness Framework (CEN-CENELEC, JTC 21, WG 4, WI=JT021008): a framework for AI systems' trustworthiness which contains terminology, concepts, high-level horizontal requirements, guidance and a method to contextualize those to specific stakeholders, domains or applications.
- ▷ EN AI Risk Management (CEN-CENELEC, JTC 21, WG 2, WI=JT021024): horizontal requirements for a risk management system for AI Systems throughout their lifecycle to prevent or minimize health, safety or fundamental rights risks.

My activity addresses EN AI Trustworthiness Framework gaps related to two aspects:

- ▷ Trustworthiness requirements on the AI System level: ISO/IEC TR 24028:2020 does not provide requirements.
- ▷ Protecting European values and fundamental rights: ISO/IEC TR 24028:2020 does not reflect the European values nor the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights.

Furthermore, the gaps addressed by EN AI Risk Management concern:

- ▷ Risk management on the AI system. ISO 31000:2018: risk management on the organisational level not tailored to use of AI systems. ISO 23894:2023 risk management related to AI on the organisational level.
- ▷ Ensuring product safety including fundamental rights for a broad range of products: Unlike many risk management standards, the EN AI Risk Management standard focusses on

'enhanced' product safety, including the protection of fundamental rights. Furthermore, it extends ISO 14971:2019 to include other products than medical devices. Unlike many risk management standards, the EN AI Risk Management standard focuses on 'enhanced' product safety, including the protection of fundamental rights.

- ▶ Enabling integrated risk management on the product and AI system level: providing methods to integrate risk management for an AI system which is a product safety component with the risk management for the overall product.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

The EN AI Trustworthiness Framework standard provides requirements for the design and management of trustworthy AI systems that proactively respect European norms and values and fundamental rights. ISO/IEC TR 24028:2020 does not provide requirements nor does it reflect the European values nor the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights.

The EN AI Trustworthiness Framework standard uses definitions from EN ISO/IEC 22989:2023. Other standards provide more detailed requirements on different AI System trustworthiness aspects: robustness (prEN ISO/IEC 24029), accuracy (prEN ISO/IEC 23282, ISO/IEC TS 4213:202), data governance and quality for AI (FprCEN/CLC/TR 18115, ISO/IEC 5259 part 1-4), transparency and documentation (prEN ISO/IEC 12792), record keeping through logging (prEN ISO/IEC 24970), cybersecurity (prEN Cybersecurity specifications for AI Systems), AI systems risk management (prEN AI Risk Management), and quality management (EN ISO/IEC 25059:2024). This standard also lays the groundwork for future vertical, product-specific Trustworthy AI standards.

The EN AI Risk Management standard complements ISO 31000:2018 and ISO 23894:2023 by providing risk management of the AI system. The prEN AI System Risk Management complements ISO 14971:2019 and ISO 12100:2010 by extending risk management to a broad range of products and by also enhancing product safety to include fundamental rights. This standard lays the groundwork for vertical/product/AI-technology-specific AI System Risk Management standards.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

The standards in general enable responsible yet affordable innovation with fast launch to market for all companies including SMEs: ensuring concrete requirements that can be integrated in existing trustworthy AI and risk management processes and day-to-day business operations.

Also, this activity impacts SMEs directly as I review and contribute to the prEN AI Trustworthiness Framework and prEN AI Risk Management accounting for the SME inclusiveness of the requirements. I want to enable SMEs to provide and/or deploy trustworthy AI systems while controlling AI risks taking into account their modest resources as compared to enterprises.

Impact on Society

EN AI Trustworthiness Framework provides requirements for trustworthy AI systems that align with European stakeholders and regulation and European values. Enable the design and management of trustworthy AI systems that proactively respect European norms and values and fundamental rights.

The EN AI Risk Management standard enables us to control risks not only on the individual and company level but also on the level of the society (e.g. misinformation and disinformation risks, risks to democratic processes, etc.). The scope of the standard indicates that risks covered include both risks to health and safety and risks to fundamental rights which can arise from AI systems, with impact for individuals, organisations, market and society.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I contribute to developing new standards, including:

- ▷ EN AI Trustworthiness Framework will result to a recommendation to provide other standards with more detailed requirements on different AI System trustworthiness aspects: e.g. on bias (e.g. prEN XXX (WI=JT021036) Artificial Intelligence - Concepts, measures and requirements for managing bias in AI systems). It will also recommend to provide AI technology specific standards as the AI Trustworthiness Standard is a horizontal and AI-technology agnostic standard: e.g. prEN XXX (WI=JT021025) Artificial Intelligence – Evaluation methods for accurate computer vision systems).
- ▷ EN AI Risk Management: This standard lays the groundwork for future vertical/product/AI-technology-specific standards. E.g. an AI risk management for GenAI/LLMs.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, my fellowship contributes to the deliverable of a FprEN AI Trustworthiness Framework and FprEN AI Risk Management.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

Yes, I see especially two future standardisation projects including the development of AI-technology/trustworthy AI aspect specific standards and AI-technology/industry specific AI risk management standards.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 [EN AI Trustworthiness Framework](#)

 [EN AI Risk Management standard](#)

Progress and lead delivery of EN AI Conformity assessment and supporting operational standards

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Sector

Artificial intelligence

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

CEN and CENELEC JTC 21 Artificial Intelligence WG 2 “Operational Aspects”
ISO/IEC JTC 1 SC 42 JWG 6 Joint Working Group ISO/IEC JTC1/SC42 - ISO/CASCO: Conformity assessment schemes for AI systems

Role

Convener CEN and CENELEC JTC 21 Artificial Intelligence WG 2 “operational aspects”

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

The EU has the potential to become a global leader in safe AI and for this to happen the EU industry needs a trustworthy framework for AI adoption and EU standards aligned with EU values play a key role.

The work I am leading in European Standardisation through the CEN and CENELEC JTC 21 WG 2, answers directly the main operational pillars of the Standardisation request received from the European Commission as to provide technical specifications through standards (candidate for harmonization) in support of the EU AI Act.

Current operational gaps include a concrete framework for AI Conformity assessment that EU AI-enabled products could follow as to prove alignment with the requirements set in the EU AI Act. My work addresses this gap and is focused on ensuring that the proposed framework will align with existing conformity assessment framework already used in highly regulated areas and will not induce large additional costs. Another important aspect is that of avoiding duplication in terms of quality management and risk management framework and allow an easy bridging for all EU AI-enabled solutions.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

The main pillar and focus of my contribution comes from my editor role for the EN AI Conformity assessment framework (under development as candidate for harmonization) on providing a comprehensive framework for AI conformity assessment of EU AI systems as products. The EN is intended to cover the gap for requirements related with post-market monitoring of AI systems and also provide a framework of conformity for AI enabled products to be placed on the European market.

The second pillar of my contribution is providing leading support as convener of CEN/CLC JTC 21 WG 2 Operational aspects for the development of the standards filling the remaining conformity assessment needs and gaps and addressing the challenge of coherence and consistency in terms of EN AI risk management and EN AI Quality management system and also with EN AI Conformity assessment framework and answering the specificity of the European legislation and European market.

My work as a whole tackles the EU AI Standardisation request priorities set up by the European Commission in the area of operational aspects (through CEN/CLC JTC 21 WG 2) needed for ensuring compliance with the EU AI Act requirements for AI systems on the EU single market.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

My work aims at providing a comprehensive operational framework of standards that enables European SMEs and European societies access the EU market while ensuring compliance with the requirements of the EU AI Act in a cost and resource efficient way.

My work as convenor and editor is focusing on providing operational standards that offer a complete coverage of the requirements of the EU AI Act. My focus is on the delivery of self-contained operational standards as the EN AI Conformity assessment for which I am editor, such that SMEs can understand their requirements without the need of additional consultancy and that SMEs would be able to directly implement these new requirements.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I contribute to the NWIP EN AI Conformity assessment standard I have proposed received positive vote for development as standard and is intended to cover in CEN and CENELEC JTC 21 WG 2, the requirement 10 of the Standardisation Request issued by the European Commission in support to the EU AI Act.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, I am the editor for the EN AI Conformity assessment framework

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The engaged standardisation project is now in progress. The EN AI Conformity assessment is currently under development of the first working draft.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:22:0:::FSP_ORG_ID,FSP_LANG_ID:2916257,25&cs=1827B89DA69577BF3631EE2B6070F207D

The AI Trustworthiness Framework - delivering a harmonized standard for the EU AI Act

Piercosma Bisconti Lucidi

Researcher in AI Ethics, Co-Founder of DEXAI – Artificial Ethics, Italian Interuniversity Consortium for Computer Science Italy

Sector

Artificial intelligence

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

**CEN/CENELEC JTC 21 AI WG4 Foundational & Societal Aspects
ISO/IEC SC 42 AI JTC1 WG3 on "AI trustworthiness"**

Role

Chair

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

For what concerns gaps, I focus on addressing the standardisation request of the EU Commission in relation to the AI Act. The grace period given to high-risk AI systems under the AI Act is 24 months, and CEN-CENELEC standardisation activities need to work at a fast pace to meet this deadline with standards ensuring AI Act practical implementation. The development of this standard represents a priority in the AI standardisation landscape to provide companies, organisations, and SMEs with an entry point to the standards for AI in the EU, and delivering the high-level requirements that will ensure the protection of fundamental rights. One of the addressed key challenges are the gaps between standards under development inside the CEN-CENELEC, and the complexity of their interplay. This issue might constitute an outstanding barrier for CEN-CENELEC standards toward a full coverage of the EU AI Act. In fact, some provisions might remain unaddressed, ultimately delaying or hindering the full application of the AI Act in the EU environment. The "AI Trustworthiness Framework" aims to fill these gaps by putting forth those requirements that remained unaddressed in order to cover the AI Act provisions, and examine the interplay between the different requirements of other standards, to understand if there are overlaps or contradictions that need to be addressed. Moreover, AI ethics is a field that is still highly qualitative and poorly systematic. I am contributing in the standardisation activities of AI Ethics to provide the EU environment with clear methodologies to address ethical challenges of AI systems.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

In my role as project leader and editor of the 'AI Trustworthiness Framework', I am guiding this crucial task group to establish an overarching standard. This standard is intended to serve as the industry entry point for the 10 items specified in the standardisation request. The concept of trustworthiness, central since the High-Level Expert Group on AI's White Paper 'Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI', defines our approach. To ensure trustworthiness in Artificial Intelligence means that AI systems are capable of 'meeting stakeholders' expectations in a verifiable way'. In the EU context, this entails that AI systems will respect and reflect EU values and fundamental rights. The objective of this task group is to support the AI standardisation

request by providing guidance and requirements to stakeholders. This guidance will inform the use of standards identified in the Architecture of Standards. The project's aim is to develop a standard on the AI trustworthiness framework that ensures actionability for all stakeholders and sectors. Its goal is to bring consistency, comprehensiveness, and alignment to high-level horizontal requirements. To achieve this, the following objectives have been set:

- ▷ Put forth high level horizontal requirements for AI systems.
- ▷ Work toward bringing consistency and harmonisation between the different standards developed under JTC21, to fill the current gaps in order to support the EU AI Act.
- ▷ Develop a contextualisation methodology to contextualize high-level horizontal requirements to specific domains of applications or stakeholders. This methodology will be a guidance on how to tailor the horizontal requirements to specific domains of applications that might require additional measures to ensure trustworthiness.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

Industries and SMEs in the EU are facilitated in adopting standards. One of the main barriers for standard adoption is the complexity of the standardisation processes. In order to claim conformity, multiple requirements coming from multiple standards should be met. The AI Trustworthiness Framework will serve as an entry point for industries and SMEs in order to facilitate this process, fostering conformity and facilitating industry competitiveness.

Impact on Society

Trustworthiness fosters social acceptance. One of the outstanding barriers in the deployment of innovative technologies is social acceptance. This barrier damages both the economic benefits and the social benefits of designing innovative AI systems. The AI Trustworthiness Framework will reinforce social trust in AI systems, by providing companies, consumers and ultimately citizens with a clear understanding of the fundamental requirements for trustworthy AI.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I am the project leader for the development of the "AI Trustworthiness Framework" that is of outstanding importance for the EU AI environment, addressing and seeking harmonisation for half of the standardisation request of the EC related to the practical implementation of the EU AI Act. This role of overarching framework and support to the implementation of the Standardisation request for trustworthiness is explicitly stated in many passages of the architecture of standards of CEN-CENELEC developed under WG1.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, I lead the development of the "AI Trustworthiness Framework" draft working documents.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The next steps are the finalisation of the draft for enquiry, and finalisation of the Annex ZA.. Then, we aim to obtain consensus and initiate the enquiry stage. During the enquiry (supposedly reduced to 8 weeks only thanks to CEN-CENELEC "fast track"), I will work on deliverables for the ethics project. Then we foresee collaborating with other working groups in ISO on ethical frameworks for AI standardisation (e.g: ISO TR 24368:2022), integrating the trustworthiness framework in the ethical considerations and aligning and/or comparing the work done with ISO WG3 and WG1.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://www.cencenelec.eu/areas-of-work/cen-cenelec-topics/artificial-intelligence/>

Standards supporting European Digital Identity Wallet and Relying Parties

Michal Tabor

Digital identity expert, Technologie Informacyjnej Michal Tabor Poland

Sector

Electronic identification

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ETSI ESI Electronic Signatures and Trust Infrastructures Liaison with CEN/TC 224 Personal identification and related personal devices with secure elements, systems, operations and privacy in a multi sectorial environment

Role

Member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

With this fellowship I address several gaps in standards in the field of electronic identification and European digital identity wallet, including:

- ▷ Lack of European standards for interfaces for Digital Identity Wallet
- ▷ Requirement of eIDAS Regulation to enable wallet to create a qualified electronic signature
- ▷ Need for recognition of Relying Parties with use of electronic seal certificates

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

This fellowship supports my work with two European standards:

Firstly, I contribute to ETSI TS 119 462 Wallet interfaces for trust services and signing. The goal of this initiative is to ensure that the Digital Identity Wallet functions uniformly across the entire EU market in a secure and interoperable manner. The ecosystem for this solution includes wallet providers, data providers to the wallet, trust service providers who issue attribute attestations to the wallet, trust service providers who issue electronic signature certificates and perform electronic signing, and relying parties (entities that trust and use the wallet).

Secondly, I work with the development of ETSI TS 119 475 Relying party authorisations for access to EUDI Wallet. It aimed at enabling all entities that trust the Digital Identity Wallet to uniformly meet the conditions required for issuing certificates. All these entities must have a standardized tool that allows them to recognize and interact with the wallet. The standard "Wallet Interfaces for Trust Services and Signing" will enable the wallet to function effectively with trust service providers, who are a critical part of the infrastructure. These providers are responsible for supplying the wallet with attribute attestations and facilitating electronic signing.

In practical terms, related to these standardisation projects, I have managed a presentation of current drafts at ETSI/CEN workshop and collected contributions to the standards. I have also validated the ongoing work against OpenID Foundation and other standardisation

bodies, which enabled the establishment of a new stable version of the standard that was presented at the ETSI ESI meeting for further collection of contributions, comments, and their disposition.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on Society

By stating that the priority is electronic identification and trust services, this work directly impacts both electronic identification and trust services. Specifically, the ETSI Standard 119 462 (Wallet Interfaces) influences identification and trust services in the following ways:

- ▶ It establishes a standardized mechanism for identification from the wallet to trust service providers.
- ▶ It creates a standardized mechanism for trust service providers to issue attributes that are used for identification.
- ▶ It sets up a mechanism for collaboration with trust service providers in the process of creating electronic signatures.

The ETSI TS 119 475 (Relying Parties Authorisations) standard enables the secure use of the wallet for identifying relying parties, ensuring a secure identification process, and managing interactions both with identification recipients and trust service providers.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I contribute to two new standards ETSI TS 119 462 Wallet interfaces for trust services and signing and ETSI TS 119 475 Relying party authorisations for access to EUDI Wallet.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, I contribute to technical specifications of the related standardisation projects.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The both projects are presented to the ETSI ESI TC at the January 2025 meeting. The aim for acceptance and publication is in February 2025.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 [ETSI TS 119 462 Wallet interfaces for trust services and signing.](#)

 [ETSI TS 119 475 Relying party authorisations for access to EUDI Wallet.](#)

European Requirements for Face and Fingerprint Products

Raul Sanchez-Reillo

Full professor, University Carlos III of Madrid
Spain

Sector

Electronic identification

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

CEN TC224 Personal identification and related personal devices with secure elements, systems, operations and privacy in a multi sectorial environment WG18 Biometrics

Role

Member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

Biometrics has become one of the accepted authentication factors to be used whenever the identity of a citizen is required. This can be used for nearly any kind of digital service, so it is essential to assure that the biometric authentication is done in a robust and secure manner. Therefore, there is the need to rapidly develop the tools needed to create a certification schema for biometric products. This is the focus of this application.

This fellowship is a follow-up to my previous fellowship (funded under open call 3) titled "European Requirements for Biometric Products" where the work has advanced significantly. The technical work is about to be finished, and it is expected that after the activation, the publication will take place in less than one year, especially for parts 1, 2 and 3.

Now, with fellowship, I have three different roles and the following tasks are being accomplished:

- ▶ As liaison officer, the current drafts will be circulated in other SDOs: ETSI/ESI, in relation to their project ETSI TS 119 461 and BIO-ITC (the Common Criteria group on biometrics).
- ▶ As editor, I collate all the comments received, propose disposition of those comments, lead the discussion of the disposition to reach a solution by consensus and apply the approved disposition of comments to each of the documents and generate the new drafts.
- ▶ As a contributor, I provide content to all current calls for contributions.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

In my WG, we are working on four Work Drafts, being handled as PWI. The 4 PWIs approved are:

- ▶ Part 1: Conformity assessment scheme and application profile definition
- ▶ Part 2: Interoperability tests
- ▶ Part 3: Functionality evaluation methodology
- ▶ Part 5: Face biometrics

In addition, Part 4 on Fingerprint biometrics will be proposed, as to also provide coverage to those products related to fingerprint recognition.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

The focus is to provide a solution in the field of electronic identification, as is based on the identification of users through biometric means. Many final solution integrators are SMEs, and they are the ones having to convince the final customer with the benefits of using their products. This is typically a challenge of these SMEs, compared to multinational enterprises. This certification scheme will allow SMEs to provide convincing certification, to all different customers, through a single evaluation, closing the gap with big enterprises, and improving their market ratio.

Impact on Society

This standard boosts the creation of a certification system for biometric solutions to be used in different scenarios. One of the first scenarios to be addressed is the remote identification of citizens using videoconference tools, i.e., using facial recognition with the users' digital devices. But other scenarios will be added during this proposal, such as the use of face recognition in the future EUDI Wallet.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I contribute to developing a multipart standard called European Requirements for Biometric Products, currently with 4 parts activated for development, and another part in New Work Item Proposal (NWIP).

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, I contribute to drafting the technical specifications for this multipart standard. Also, I gave a presentation at the "ETSI / CEN Workshop on EU Digital Identity Framework Standards", that took place on September 10-12, 2024⁶, with a large audience, including the European Commission.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The formal Vote is expected to happen in short time for parts 1, 2 and 3, but part 5 will need further work to finish the Application Profiles and debugging the applicable tests. Regarding Part 4, the status is quite immature, so further work will be required to define the tests and the Application Profiles.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:7:0:::FSP_ORG_ID:6205&cs=1E59B4D3EFD280E27AAC0C16CC13CD4FD

6 <https://www.etsi.org/events/2353-cen-etsi-workshop>

Advance on-card biometric comparison standards ISO/IEC 24787, 7816-11, 17839, 18584 series

Ieva Kersiene

Senior Software Engineer, APPSCARD GROUP AS
Lithuania

Sector

Electronic identification

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 17/WG 11 - Application of biometrics to cards and personal identification (current fellowship main contribution WG)
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 37/WG 2 - Biometric technical interfaces (referenced standards)
ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 37/WG 3 - Biometric data interchange formats (referenced standards)

Role

Member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

With this fellowship, I contribute to the Biometric System-on-Card (BSoC) and On-Card Comparison (OCC) related interindustry ISO/IEC standards address the following three key aspects:

- ▶ **Bridging Definition Gaps:** Bridging existing gaps in definitions in the ISO/IEC 17839 and ISO/IEC 24787 series, specifically focusing on core, physical dimensions, and logical information exchange interfaces requirements. This involves a comprehensive examination of the latest hardware and software advancements prevalent in the market for biometric on-card verification-enabled smart cards also evaluating the need for potential scope extension to other non-smart card form factor holder verification devices with supplementary (e.g., BLE, NFC) communication interface support. The emphasis is on ensuring that the standards are not solely rooted in theory but are backed by practical use cases.
- ▶ **Enhancing Clarity and Consistency:** Addressing the ongoing challenge involves maintaining clarity and consistency in any standards revisions developed by ISO/IEC JTC1/SC17/WG11 (e.g., ISO/IEC 7816-11), particularly concerning other Standard Committees (SCs) and Working Groups (WGs) developed standards. This effort includes eliminating ambiguities and ensuring seamless alignment with cross-referenced ISO/IEC JTC1 SC37/WG3 and SC37/WG2 (e.g., ISO/IEC 19785-3) standards on BDIF (Biometric Data Interchange Formats) and CBEFF (Common Biometric Exchange Formats Framework) interfaces and formats.
- ▶ **Prioritising Practical Applicability:** The standards development process places a significant emphasis on practical applicability by aiming for seamless integration in real-world interoperable scenarios. The main goal is to facilitate the straightforward integration, testing (e.g., through ISO/IEC 18584 series) and maintenance of the standard compliant biometric solutions within diverse-scale interindustry biometric systems, which typically accommodate hardware and software components provided by various vendors

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

My work addresses the ISO/IEC 24787 series co-editorship by receiving comments review, collation with other editors for PDoC (Proposed Disposition of Comments).

The ongoing contributions also encompass the most recent submissions of comments following the balloting process for the development of the following ISO/IEC standards:

- ▶ 24787-1:2024 - Information technology — On-card biometric comparison -- Part 1: General principles and specifications for potential Corrigendum / Amendment x 2 ballots.
- ▶ 24787-2:2024 - Information technology — On-card biometric comparison -- Part 2: Work-sharing mechanism for potential Corrigendum / Amendment x 2 ballots.
- ▶ 18584-1 DIS Information technology – Test methods for on-card biometric comparison applications — Part 1: General principles and specifications for full compliance with ISO/IEC 24787-1.
- ▶ 18584-2 DIS Information technology – Test methods for on-card biometric comparison applications — Part 2: Work-sharing mechanism for full compliance with ISO/IEC 24787-2.
- ▶ 7816-11:2022 Identification cards — Integrated circuit cards – Part 11: Personal verification through biometric methods for potential Standard Revision (SR).

Additionally, proactively participating in discussion per comments resolution and possible scope extension to non-card form factor card holder devices and / or additional interfaces:

- ▶ ISO/IEC 17839-1 CD & CD2 - Information technology — Biometric System-on-Card — Part 1: Core requirements.
- ▶ ISO/IEC 17839-3 CD & CD2 - Information technology — Biometric System-on-Card — Part 3: Logical information interchange mechanism.

Participating in liaison (with SC17/WG11) and separate ISO/IEC WG2 meeting on possible conflict with SC37/WG2 authored CBEFF ISO/IEC 19785-3 DIS (now FDIS) due to defect report to WG11 regarding ISO/IEC 7816-11:2022 and the best resolution approach.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

Currently, global biometric authentication systems are widely deployed for diverse public and commercial services authorisation. Common form factor smart cards, incorporating biometric capture and comparison within the card, offer a secure, sterile, and user-friendly experience for cardholders. Standards for Biometric System-on-Card (BSoC) and On-Card Comparison (OCC) solutions ensure compatibility with deployed interoperable biometric systems, enabling straightforward maintenance and upgrades, while avoiding vendor lock-in and proprietary limitations

Impact on Society

Multi-application smart cards are already widely deployed and used nowadays in eGovernment, ePayment, eHealth and other domains. Addition of biometric authentication enhances reliability (more secure than PIN), safety and convenience (hygienic, no need to touch PINpads or terminals sensor in case of BSoC especially while pandemic), reference card holder data security (no vulnerable and GDPR sensitive central database for biometrics is needed, card holder data cannot be read out from stolen / lost smart cards) and availability (users with no education in poor countries to obtain subsidy).

However, ISO/IEC standards shall assure consistent and unified reference for interoperable biometric data and smart card command exchange formats used, clear definition of physical characteristics based on practical use cases and the most recent advancements in HW & SW available on the market for biometric on-card verification enabled smart cards.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

In the framework of this fellowship, the ongoing contributions encompass further evolution of the standards under development towards publication (18584-x series, 17839-1/-3), and initiation the revision (SR) for existing published standards (7816-11, 24787-x series) to:

- ▶ Facilitate the consistency with current SC17/WG11 and other WGs (SC17/WG4, SC37/WG2, SC37/WG3) cross-referenced standards.
- ▶ Extend the scope from traditional smart card form factor based on initiated WG11 study. I have personally submitted specific general and technical comments in favour of new SRs initiation per internal WG11 consultation ballots.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, I am the co-editor of ISO/IEC 24787 series managing the review of received comments.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

My contribution on multiple SC17/WG11 standards in progress in different revision stages CD/CD2, DIS along with plans to initiate new Standard Revision (SR) with scope extension per already published standards. Thus, the work is ongoing.

Moreover, new SRs will rely on initiated WG11 study and worldwide call for contributions on scope extension from pure biometric verification-enabled smart card form factor to generalized biometric verification-enabled devices with potential support of extended communication interfaces and protocols (e.g., BLE) complementary to traditional smart cards' ISO/IEC 7816-x contact based and 14443-x contactless interfaces. Thus, in practice additional EU experts' participation to better support and express the EU position and expertise is always encouraged.

Online references related to the fellowship work

www.iso.org/committee/45144.html

www.iso.org/committee/313770.html

Application Benchmarks for Quantum Computers

Michele Amoretti
Associate Professor, University of Parma
Italy

Sector

Quantum Technologies

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

CEN-CENELEC JTC22 Quantum technologies WG1 “Strategic Advisory Group”
CEN-CENELEC JTC22 WG3 “Quantum Computing and Simulation”.
IEC/ISO JTC3 AHG5 “Quantum Computing and Simulation”.

Role

Member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

The lack of standard benchmarks for quantum computers is currently a major gap. In this Fellowship project, my activity concerns the effective characterisation of quantum computing systems. Namely, I pursue the two key objectives; firstly, I focus on providing guidelines on how to benchmark universal and gate-based quantum systems by means of hardware-agnostic applications. Secondly, I design two application benchmarks, because of my expertise, I mostly focus on software aspects.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

I am contributing to CEN-CENELEC JTC 22’s Working Group 3 (JTC22/WG3) “Quantum Computing and Simulation”. I have been a member of JTC22/WG3 since its foundation. There are three main activities being carried out in that working group, namely: Layer Model of Quantum Computing, Hybridisation of Quantum Computing, and Performance Benchmarks of Quantum Computing Applications.

Within JTC22/WG3, I joined a Task Force that is writing a Preliminary Work Item / Technical Report entitled “Performance benchmarks of quantum computing applications”.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

My contributions in JTC22/WG3 are mostly related to quantum software, i.e., software that is executed on quantum computers but also software that is executed on classical computers for enabling/supporting quantum computations. In Europe, new SMEs are growing around the quantum software topic. Therefore, I feel that the activity I am carrying out in the context of JTC22/WG3 will be beneficial for those companies.

Impact on Society

Quantum application benchmarking will benefit industrial end-users, quantum computing manufacturers (hardware and software) and Governments. The general intent is to fulfil their needs for objective performance comparison of emerging quantum processors, providing application benchmarks with specific metrics and methodologies.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes. Within the JTC3/WG3 Task Force that is writing a Preliminary Work Item / Technical Report entitled "Performance benchmarks of quantum computing applications", I am contributing to the main section on application-level metrics and benchmarks. It is planned to release a first version of the PWI/TR by June 2025.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, I am contributing to the technical report as described in the section above.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The documents I produced, and those I will produce in the next months, concerning the activities of JTC22/WG3, are contributions to a Technical Reports (of PWI type) that is work in progress. Each contribution concerns a specific section of the TR and may be further updated in next months

Online references related to the fellowship work

 www.cencenelec.eu/areas-of-work/cen-cenelec-topics/quantum-technologies/

3. Innovation for Digital Single Market

Use case submission selection to First Draft WD - ISO AWI 24878 New and emerging DLT use cases

Fiona Delaney

*IT Researcher, Origin Chain Networks
Ireland*

Sector

Blockchain and distributed ledger technologies

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO TC307 Blockchain and DLT WG6 Use cases
ISO/CEN JWG 19 Blockchain and DLT

Role

Member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

My fellowship focuses on developing use cases for Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technology. ISO AWI 24878 builds upon standards development work in ISO 3242:2022, ISO 6039:2023 and ISO 6277:2024. A journey of discovery is underway to identify emerging application domains and novel business applications for blockchain and DLT internationally. At our WG's 14th Plenary in Valladolid, 11 new use cases were introduced to WG6, demonstrating a wide variety and global breadth of submission (8 being from the EU):

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

With this fellowship, I focus on drafting ISO/AWI TR 24878 New and emerging DLT/Blockchain Use Cases (ed.1 - id.88315), which passed by resolution at the 13th ISO/TC307 Plenary. An additional five use cases are also in the pipeline. Not all of these use cases will be selected for inclusion in the Working Draft that goes to the ballot. Still, each takes about one working day to onboard and shepherd through the use case submission process, whereupon they must be validated for completeness of both the written description and system visualisation models before presenting them at WG6 for discussion.

This fellowship project covers the time involved in preparing the first Working Draft (WD) that ultimately yields the WD put forward for the Committee Ballot.

It is clear that many insights can be achieved through discourse and consensus in open standards development. More widely, through publication, sharing insights from use case analysis enhances industry know-how and provides evidence for regulators and industry alike of the stability, security and completeness of emerging applications in blockchain.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

My work stems from my perspective as a former blockchain Startup, now an SME. My focus is on spotlighting real-world use cases to contextualise the technology. This is impactful in that it spotlights challenges and opportunities from many perspectives and may inspire the establishment of new businesses and services that enhance privacy, trust, and security in our

digital society in transformation.

Impact on Society

My project has so far clustered received use cases according to the three most common Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) that underpin the current set of use cases in the report:

SDG 9 - Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure - Build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialisation and foster innovation - (6 use cases: 3 x open standards; 1 x in production; 2 x proof of concepts)

SDG 11 - Sustainable Cities and Communities - Make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable - (3 use cases: 1 x in production, 2 x proof of concepts)

SDG 16 - Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions - Promote peaceful and inclusive societies for sustainable development, provide access to justice for all and build effective, accountable and inclusive institutions at all levels - (3 use cases: 1 x open standard; 1 x in production; 1 x proof of concept)

In each of these areas, blockchain/DLT technology is deployed to enhance, enforce or incentivise good governance and cooperative behaviours across multi-party systems.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I contribute to developing new standards. The valuable work at ISO TC307 WG6 is well-received, and a further Work Item has been approved at the 13th Plenary to explore standardising a use case description template and the viability of conformance pathways for blockchain and DLT use cases.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, I have contributed to a technical report on developing a new standard.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The set of use cases in the report will be reduced to limit repetition and redundancy. This process must be achieved through formal consensus and will inevitably take time. There remain some gaps in essential topic areas that I hope to see filled within the next stage of the work.

Online references related to the fellowship work

www.iso.org/committee/6266604.html

Core Standards for Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technology and Digital Currencies

Geoffrey Goodell

*Lecturer in Financial Computing, University College London
United Kingdom*

Sector

Blockchain and distributed ledger technologies

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO/TC 68/JWG 1 “Digital Currencies”
ISO/TC 46/SC 11/JWG 1 “Blockchain”
ISO/TC 307/AG 3 “Digital Currencies”
ISO/TC 307/AHG 5 “Foundations Review”
ISO/TC 68 Financial Services
CEN/CLC/JTC 19

Role

- ▷ Convenor ISO/TC 307/AG 3 “Digital Currencies”
- ▷ Convenor ISO/TC 307/AHG 5 “Foundations Review”
- ▷ Co-Convenor ISO/TC 46/SC 11/JWG 1 “Blockchain”
- ▷ Co-Convenor ISO/TC 68/JWG 1 “Digital Currencies”
- ▷ ISO/TC 307 as head of UK mirror committee
- ▷ Expert member in other groups

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

In the framework of this fellowship, our work in ISO directly supports EU objectives in both the ‘Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technologies’ and ‘Fintech and Regtech Standardisation’ topic areas, particularly in the context of digital currencies, which shall be supported by a new standard, ‘Digital Currencies – Vocabulary’ (ISO/AWI 24982). This standard addresses a major challenge facing businesses and governments around the world concerning consistency of language for describing the technology and infrastructure underlying digital currencies (including CBDC) and decentralised finance. Our work also supports ‘Citizen centric digital public services’, ‘ePrivacy’, ‘Identity Management and Anonymisation’, ‘Privacy protection’, and ‘Smart Contracts’, all of which will be supported by potential revisions to ‘Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technology – Vocabulary’ (ISO 22739:2024) and ‘Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technology – Reference Architecture’ (ISO 23257:2022). Our technical report on Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technology in relation to authoritative records, records systems, and records management (ISO/DTR 24332) is close to publication and will address challenges related to determination of the legal status of records in DLT systems and their suitability for institutional record management.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

ISO/DTR 24332 'Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technology in relation to authoritative records, records systems, and records management', which has reached consensus to advance its most recent draft to Enquiry (DTR) stage, and which is assigned to ISO/TC 46/SC 11/JWG 1, a working group for which I serve as Co-Convenor.

ISO/AWI 24982 'Digital currencies – Vocabulary', which is assigned to ISO/TC 68/JWG 1, for which I serve as Co-Convenor.

Possible revisions to ISO 22739:2024 'Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technologies – Vocabulary' and 'Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technology – Reference Architecture' (ISO 23257:2022), which were developed by a working group that I convened (ISO/TC 307/WG 1) and for which a study on a possible revision has been assigned to an ad hoc group that I convene, ISO/TC 307/AHG 5.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

The standards that we are developing support the use of distributed ledgers, which are a core enabling technology for a plethora of applications, including tracking the provenance of assets, achieving decentralised agreement in creating documents, streamlining the reconciliation of transactions, and facilitating the transfer of value via tokenisation. DLT can facilitate and enhance a wide variety of commercial activities among European businesses and feature prominently in active development of European regulations, including but not limited to eIDAS and EBSI.

Impact on Society

Distributed ledger technology offers an opportunity to promote better management of data within public services, including for accounting and records management, as well as for electronic payments, particularly in the context of digital currencies, which represent an opportunity for central banks and financial regulators to provide a public payment mechanism that citizen-consumers can use independently of potentially exclusive custodial relationships. As a means to provide citizen-consumers with democratic, cash-like bearer instruments, the value of tokenisation should not be understated, as the use of cash in much of the EU is declining, raising the question of whether our cash infrastructure will be economically sustainable over the long-term.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

In my role as convenor, I support both development and revision of standards. At the moment of this fellowship, ISO/TC 307/AHG 5, which I convene, is tasked with reviewing ISO 22739:2024 and ISO 23257:2022 to determine whether a revision is necessary at this time. If this group determines that a revision is indeed necessary, then it may develop a draft NWIP or NWIPs correspondingly.

In parallel, ISO/TC 307/AG 3, which I convene, has expressed support for, in the fullness of time, a new work item on Digital Currencies – Taxonomy and Ontology, which we anticipate would be assigned to ISO/TC 68/JWG 1, which I co-convene.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, as an example: ISO/DTR 24332 is currently under the DTR/FDIS ballot, which is expected to close in about two weeks. The document is already in stage 50.20, so hopefully publication will be done in early 2025.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

Meetings of ISO/TC 68/JWG 1 to develop ISO/AWI 24982 have begun. We have held nine meetings so far, and we expect to have a first WD in early 2025. Also, meetings of ISO/TC 307/AHG 5 to determine whether to revise ISO 22739:2024 and ISO 23257:2022 have begun. We have held one meeting so far, and three more meetings are scheduled. We anticipate deciding upon a direction by early February 2025, and delivering a finalised report, and possibly one or more NWIP documents, by April.

Technical Editor ISO/IEC 27566 Age Assurance Systems - Framework

Tony Allen

Technical Editor - ISO Project AVID Certification Services Ltd
United Kingdom

Sector

Fintech and regtech

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO/IEC JTC1 SC27 WG5 - Identity and Privacy Management

Role

Technical Editor for the ISO/IEC 27566 series.

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

My fellowship is a continuation to my previous fellowships that address the standardisation of age assurance systems, which is a priority to ensure compliance with regulations like the EU's Digital Services Act and GDPR. Key challenges include harmonising international standards, ensuring privacy and data minimisation, and achieving interoperability between systems. These standards aim to provide a framework for child protection, prevent misuse, and establish benchmarks for age verification across industries.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

This fellowship is a follow-up activity to my previous StandICT.eu2026 Open Call #2 fellowship, and it supports my engagement in the development of the ISO/IEC 27566 series:

- ▷ ISO/IEC 27566-1: Framework for Age Assurance Systems, which has progressed to the DIS (Draft International Standard) enquiry stage, with publication anticipated in 2025.
- ▷ ISO/IEC 27566-2: Benchmarks for Benchmarking Analysis, currently advancing through working draft stages.
- ▷ ISO/IEC 27566-3: Interoperability, Technical Architecture, and Guidelines for Use, at the preliminary work item stage, aiming for progression in 2025 and publication by 2027

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

This work benefits European SMEs by creating a uniform framework for age verification that aligns with EU regulatory standards like GDPR and the Digital Services Act. The societal impact includes fostering safer online environments, protecting children from exploitation, and promoting accountability in industries like healthcare, education, and digital content.

Impact on Society

This standards series has a strong societal impact, notably it:

- ▷ Enables policy makers to determine and set requirements for indicators of confidence in age assurance processes
- ▷ Enables government to regulate age eligibility restrictions with confidence, utilising

reference to international standards in guidance, codes, licensed operator conditions, regulation and specifications

- ▶ Enables government to promote growth of age assurance processes, with confidence (through ISO requirements utilised in international accreditation processes) of the conformity assessment of those services.
- ▶ Provides consumers with trusted certified systems for providing age assurance, commensurate with risk and policy decisions and within an international standards framework.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I am contributing to the development of ISO/IEC 27566 series standards for age assurance systems, addressing framework, benchmarks, and interoperability.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, the deliverables include working drafts for:

- ▶ ISO/IEC 27566-1 DIS enquiry.
- ▶ ISO/IEC 27566-2 and 27566-3 progress through iterative drafts.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

ISO/IEC 27566-1 has advanced to the DIS enquiry stage, while Parts 2 and 3 are progressing through drafts. These efforts align with the timelines for publication in 2025 and 2027, respectively.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://www.iso.org/committee/45306.html>

Leading the development of ITU standards for IoT and Metaverse in smart cities and communities

Marios Angelopoulos

*Professor of Networked and Sensing Systems, Bournemouth University
United Kingdom*

Sector

Smart cities

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ITU-T Study Group 20 “Internet of Things, smart cities and communities”

Role

Co-Chair of ITU-T SG 20

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

My work in ITU addresses the priorities of the call pertaining to smart cities and communities, technologies and services for smart and efficient energy use, and citizen centric digital public services and EMC radiation. The work is highly relevant to the European Commission’s strategy for Europe as the development of standards provisioning the use of crowdsourcing methodologies is aligned with one of the nine initiatives mentioned in a recent report by the European Commission DG Communications Networks, Content & Technology to lead the way is ‘empowering cities and communities across Europe’ through ‘better public services for citizens, better use of resources and less impact on the environment’. Furthermore, crowdsourcing methods enable the re-purposing of privately owned digital assets (such as smartphones) and therefore in line with sustainability and the transition to a Circular Economy as described in the Green Deal.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

This StandICT.eu fellowship supports my engagement and contribution to the International Standardisation Union (ITU), one of the most prominent and impactful SDOs in the area of ICT with a global outreach to policy makers, Industry and Academia. In particular, the fellowship supports me in my role as Co-Rapporteur of Question 5 “Study of emerging digital technologies, terminology and definitions” in ITU-T Study Group 20 “Internet of Things, smart cities and communities”. Currently SG20/Q5 has five active work items covering areas such as blockchain terms and definitions for IoT, digital transformation, and smart oceans. Furthermore, I also lead the editorship of a work item for ITU Technical Report YSTR.P2P-CC “Current state of P2P crowd charging platforms and corresponding market needs”.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

According to Allied Market Research, the Wireless Power Transfer market is projected to be worth USD 35 Billion by 2030 at a 27 CAGR. The development of international standards will

help provide SMEs, policy makers and regulators with common references thus helping overcome market barriers such as technology fragmentation, thus promoting market growth.

Impact on Society

A clear trend is being formed of moving from vertical energy management that distributes energy in a wired, centralized manner towards more open and distributed architectures adopted close to the edge of the population networks, which among other technologies also utilize the wireless power potential. In this new paradigm, energy will be distributed, shared and managed locally, thus closing the distance between citizens and the available energy sources.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I lead the editorship of a work item for ITU Technical Report YSTR.P2P-CC "Current state of P2P crowd charging platforms and corresponding market needs"

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, I am the main editor of the technical report mentioned above.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The technical report is currently under development with two draft versions having been approved by Q5/SG20 meeting. Also, I continue the work in collaboration with other delegations in progressing the established work item. I also pursue my participation in and chairing of any ad-hoc rapporteur meetings.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 www.itu.int/en/ITU-T/studygroups/2022-2024/20/Pages/default.aspx

4. Sustainable growth

DPP standards and ICT products: digital information on sustainability and circularity

Leandro Navarro

*Professor, Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya
Spain*

Sector

Digital product passport

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ITU-T Study Group 5 Environment and circular economy Q7 e-waste, circular economy and sustainable supply chain management
ETSI DES/EE-EEPS64

Role

Co-Chair

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

The gap is to provide guidelines for the implementation of ITU T.L1071 / ETSI ES 204 082 standard in the context of the digital product passport to express environmental sustainability and circularity information to facilitate checking the alignment of ICT products to standards. The priorities identified are: Circular Economy, Safety, Transparency and Due Process Online, Privacy protection, Building Trust. The technical challenge is providing a clear direction and method through examples of 1) information templates about a standard (following L.1071) that include a set of expected claims or tables, and 2) description of environmental information about a product, that can be mapped to UNTP B2B DPP claim data instances. The timing challenge is to inform developers of first-generation data space for ICT products to take this standard into account for the first generation of DPP for ICT product policies and implementations.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

This fellowship is helping in my role as editor and co-rapporteur after the development of a standard for the development of an information model for digital product information on sustainability and circularity. The ITU-T work item is L1071 (L.D4PI work item) and the technical aligned ETSI ES 204 082 standards (ETSI DES/EE-EEPS64 work item).

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on Society

The resulting standard element from this work will support legislative initiatives in the EU for implementing the digital product passport for ICT products in Europe and globally. This work focuses on environmental information for ICT products, and is complementary to other digital standards about the DPP in Europe and globally. Also, this is a relevant standard for any size organisation that produces or modifies ICT products that are part, involved in any stage, of the circular economy

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

No directly: my fellowship involves the already published ITU-T LI071 and ETSI ES 204 082 standard on an information model for digital product information on sustainability and circularity. It provides guidelines for implementation of that standard, and therefore it may accompany or be referenced in the revised standard.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, I mentioned above, I am contributing to the guidelines for the implementation of two standards. In addition, this work was presented at ETSI and ITU Symposium on ICT Sustainability: Standards Driving Environmental Innovation (Geneva, Switzerland, 11-12, December 2024/Session 7: Digital Product Passport: Navigating Environmental Transparency in ICTs)⁷.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

Once these guidelines and examples are finalised, these will be shared as a contribution to ITU and ETSI and these can accompany or reference new standardisation projects in the domain.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://www.itu.int/en/ITU-T/about/groups/Pages/sg05.aspx>

⁷ <https://www.itu.int/en/ITU-T/Workshops-and-Seminars/2024/1211/Pages/programme.aspx>

Industrial Data Ontology and Industrial Ontology Foundry: Tooling and Ontology Contributions

Vladimir Alexiev

Chief Data Architect, Sirma AI (Ontotext Corp)
Bulgaria

Sector

Digitisation of European industry

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO/TC184/SC4/WG26 Ontology Based Interoperability
Industrial Digital Twin Association (IDTA) Semantics WG for AAS
Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) GeoSPARQL 1.3 WG
OGC CityGML WG
QUDT Technical Advisory Board (TAB)
W3C Data Shapes WG reconstituted for SHACL 1.2

Role

Member and editor in W3C Data Shapes of the SHACL Compact specification;

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

There are a large number of sector-specific data models. Semantic technologies offer opportunities to integrate and harmonize such models within and between enterprises and industries. This is especially useful in inter-disciplinary data analysis scenarios. However, many standardisation communities are not familiar with ontologies, semantic data modeling, and tools to facilitate their creation and maintenance.

One of the main gaps that I am tackling with this activity is that many important standards are published only as PDF, without global identifiers (URLs) that can be used in requirements and test management, and without technical artefacts like datasets, schemas, test cases. W3C is a good exception: its specifications have anchors for every important clause, and are always accompanied by Use Case Reports and Conformance Tests. The tests and implementation conformance results are machine-readable (using the Test Manifest and EARL ontologies respectively). But few SDOs follow such practices.

Communities that already use semantics, do it in various non-standards ways.

Moreover, semantic artefacts are described at various levels (RDF, SKOS thesauri, RDFS ontologies, OWL ontologies, SHACL shapes). Some (even established) communities use ontological constructs incorrectly, and don't follow best practices. Also, semantic artefacts are generated from UML models in various ways that are not compatible with each other

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

In the framework of this fellowship I have participated in semantic developments of a number of standards:

- ▶ Industrial Data Ontology (IDO) as a high-level ontology for industrial data
- ▶ Asset Administration Shell (AAS) for Industry 4.0 and manufacturing digital twins

- ▷ Dataspace Protocol (DSP) for EU sovereign data exchange
- ▷ GeoSPARQL for geospatial information
- ▷ CityGML as RDF for smart city (architecture, landscape, transportation etc)
- ▷ Quantities, Units and Datatypes ontology (QUDT) for units of measure and quantity kinds
- ▷ UN Transparency Protocol (UNTP) for verifiable claims on goods origin, quality, energy efficiency, climate impact, circularity
- ▷ ERA Vocabulary (also SKOS thesauri, SHACL shapes and RDF instance data) for rail data
- ▷ Shapes Constraint Language (SHACL 1.2) for modeling and validation of RDF data

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

Semantic data integration has numerous benefits for handling complex and diverse data. Knowledge Graphs are picking up in popularity in many Industrial domains. They are used by large and small companies alike, and there is plenty of collaboration within and between industries. Europe is a leader in this domain.

Impact on Society

The following European goals can be facilitated greatly by elaborating inter-disciplinary data integration based on ontologies and semantic technologies:

- ▷ smart manufacturing
- ▷ green transition
- ▷ circular economy
- ▷ industry digitalisation including industry 4.0 and digital twins
- ▷ data economy (single digital market) including data spaces
- ▷ artificial intelligence including knowledge graphs and semantisation of data models

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I contribute to several new standardisation projects mentioned above.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, I contribute especially to technical specifications.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

During the next 3 months I'll focus more on tooling, but will continue my semantic contributions to a variety of standards and important ontologies.

In particular, I hope for a very interesting engagement with the ISO/IEC Smart project, which aims to semantize some aspects of standards publication of the two most important SDOs, potentially including: permanent URLs for standards clauses (importing some ideas from European Legislation Identifier (ELI)), ontology review and potential reuse of the Semantic Publishing and Referencing (SPAR) ontologies, emitting Requirements Interchange Format (ReqIF), semantisation of the Relaton bibliographic database.

Moreover, ISO is in stage DIS (Draft International Standard). My tool "rdfpuml" is used for making the diagrams, and my contributions are in alignment to GeoSPARQL and QUDT ("draft" status). Where as the other key work items are:

- ▷ CityGML as RDF is available in Incubator status⁸

8 <https://github.com/ogcincubator/cityrdf>

- GeoSPARQL 1.3 will be published in a year
- SHACL 1.2 will be published in about 2 years

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://www.ogc.org/fr/publications/standard/geosparql/>

 <https://www.iso.org/committee/54158.html>

Blockchain for a Sustainable Future: Dual-Impact Standards for ESG and SDGs

Sandra Feliciano

Founder and CEO, AESTAS INSIGNIS - Investigação e Suportes de Apoio à Gestão, Unipessoal, Lda.

Portugal

Sector

ICT environmental impact

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

IPQ/CT 208 Blockchain | ISO/TC 307 Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technologies/WG 3 Smart contracts and their applications
CEN-CLC/JTC 19 Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technologies/WG 2 Environmental sustainability
IWA 48 (ISO Workshop on ESG Principles)

Role

Member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

This fellowship addresses gaps that concern the fact that current standards fail to provide clear methodologies for assessing and mitigating the environmental impact of blockchain technologies. There is also a lack of guidance on leveraging blockchain for achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and integrating Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) principles.

Hence, the priority is to align the activities with the EU's sustainability goals under the Green Deal and focus on developing standards that drive blockchain's responsible deployment. Key priorities include creating a classification system for consensus mechanisms based on their sustainability impact, ensuring smart contracts are utilized to support SDGs, and integrating ESG principles into blockchain technologies.

The main challenge is blockchain's environmental footprint, particularly energy consumption and e-waste, conflicts with sustainability objectives. Furthermore, there is fragmentation in the global adoption of sustainable blockchain practices, which this project seeks to address by establishing clear, European and internationally recognized standards.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

With this fellowship, I support the development of three key standards:

- ▶ IWA 48: Develops a framework for implementing ESG principles, offering a comprehensive perspective on governance and sustainability integration. This standard has already been finished and published since the beginning of this Fellowship. Content can be accessed online, and a pdf copy can be downloaded, both free of charge, at the ISO Online Browsing Platform (OBP) at the following link: <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/en/#iso:std:iso:iwa:48:ed-1:v1:en>
- ▶ ISO/AWI PAS 24874: Provides a guidebook for using smart contracts to achieve Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), ensuring that blockchain applications contribute to broader societal objectives.

- ▷ prCEN/CLC/TR XXX: Establishes an environmental and sustainability classification methodology for blockchain consensus mechanisms, helping stakeholders select energy-efficient and sustainable solutions.

These standards support the European Green Deal and align digital transformation with sustainability objectives. They strengthen the ICT Standards landscape by creating practical tools and frameworks that policymakers, businesses, and other stakeholders can adopt to align technology development with climate neutrality and societal well-being.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

Yes, this fellowship has an impact on European SMEs and societies by fostering sustainable innovation and creating opportunities in the blockchain sector. For SMEs, the development of clear, actionable standards enables them to adopt and implement blockchain technologies in a sustainable manner. This enhances their competitiveness in the global market, meeting growing demands for environmentally and socially responsible technologies while reducing operational risks and compliance costs.

Impact on Society

For European societies, the integration of blockchain with sustainability goals supports societal well-being by promoting transparency, reducing fraud, and enabling efficient decentralized resource management. These advancements contribute to the European Green Deal's objectives, aligning technological growth with climate neutrality and equitable development.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, I contribute to the development of three new key standards mentioned above.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Not yet.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

Contribution to IWA 48, to which I contributed with circa 50 comments at the first round of consultation, is completed and the document is published and freely available to the public⁹.

Furthermore, my contributions to ISO/AWI PAS 24874 and prCEN/CLC/TR XXX are pending due to the pending access to the registration at the respective Technical Committees and Work Groups, so I can start participating in meetings, analysing drafts and contributing with comments to improve or further develop their contents. I shall start work on this as soon as this administrative issue is resolved.

Online references related to the fellowship work

<https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/en/#iso:std:iso:iwa:48:ed-1:v1:en>

https://standards.cencenelec.eu/dyn/www/f?p=205:7:0:::FSP_ORG_ID:2702172&cs=148F2B917E4B67BCFD6FE36CE0EA923AC

⁹ <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/en/#iso:std:iso:iwa:48:ed-1:v1:en>

Bridging the gap between EU R&I ecosystem and worldwide standardisation on Smart Energy

Olivier Genest

CEO, Trialog
France

Sector

Smart grids and smart metering

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

IEC SyC Smart Energy JWG3
IEC SyC Smart Energy CAG
ISO/IEC JTC1/SC41 AG6
CEN/CLC/ETSI CG-SG

Role

Co-Convener of IEC SyC Smart Energy JWG3 and member in other groups

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

The IEC System Committee Smart Energy deals with systems level standardisation, coordination and guidance in the areas of Smart Grid and Smart Energy. The JWG3 “Smart Energy Roadmap” is a joint Working Group between the IEC SyC Smart Energy and the ISO/IEC JTC1/SC41 which focuses on Internet of Things and Digital Twin.

As Co-Convener of this JWG3, I am leading the work on IEC TR 63097 update and on Digital Twins for the electrical energy system. In addition, I am making sure that the EU R&I results/experience from BRIDGE, ETIP SNET, OPEN-DEI and int:net are taken into account at worldwide standardisation level, with the support of CEN/CLC/ETSI CG-SG, and I am disseminating the relevant on-going standardisation activities to the four abovementioned initiatives.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

My fellowship activity is organised in four key tasks that are the following:

- ▶ Task 1 work on standardisation roadmap at SyC-SE/SC41 JWG3
- ▶ Task 2 work on IoT and digital twin for energy within SyC-SE/SC41 JWG3
- ▶ Task 3 work on the Generic Actor List for CEN/CENELEC CG-SG and BRIDGE
- ▶ Task 4 work on data spaces standardisation for the energy domain. Here I am to bring ISO/IEC data spaces standardisation landscape to IEC SyC Smart Energy JWG3 and CEN/CLC/ETSI CG-SG. Bring data spaces results from EU, in particular on the Common European Energy Data Space, to IEC and ISO/IEC ecosystem, and build a roadmap for the inclusion of data spaces into IEC SyC Smart Energy workplan

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

The impact on European SMEs is twofold:

Firstly, my company Trialog is a European SME, which is impacted by my contribution. In particular, my activities in IEC SyC Smart Energy and ISO/IEC JTC1/SC41 allow me to be aware of on-going standards development in the field of IoT and Smart Energy, which is crucial for a company providing consulting and expertise on innovation. Also, my activities in the EU R&I ecosystem allow me to share experience based on our R&I projects and to learn from the experience of other projects and actors.

Secondly, the European SMEs from the smart energy sector, in particular those involved in EU R&I projects. Especially, worldwide standards are better aligned with the EU R&I ecosystem, making it easier for European SMEs to make business at worldwide level.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, with this fellowship I contribute to both, considering a new standard on Digital Twins for the electrical energy system and revising an existing one, IEC TR 63097 Smart Energy Roadmap.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes. We hosted a workshop on Digital Twins for the electrical energy system, online, September 3rd, 2024¹⁰. And I contributed to a webinar on IEC 63097 Smart Energy Roadmap¹¹

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The liaisons between EU smart energy R&I ecosystem and worldwide standardisation are on-going and active. The IEC SRD 63097 update is on-going: four batches have already been completed and published on IEC SyC SE website, and two additional batches are currently being updated.

Furthermore, the activities between BRIDGE and CEN/CENELEC/ETSI CG-SG on the update of the Generic Actor List have started: an iterative approach is on-going, allowing a step-by-step update of the list and cooperation with the relevant stakeholders of each domain. Also, a workshop on Digital Twins for the electrical energy system has been organised on September 3rd and a conclusion with an action plan has been established.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 https://iec.ch/ords/f?p=103:14:703506598282:::FSP_ORG_ID:12621

¹⁰ <https://www.iec.ch/academy/webinars/workshop-digital-twins-electrical-energy-system>

¹¹ www.youtube.com/watch?v=0ao1ytjNRi8&list=PLbOXprZa0an2aPvjwVMNWzk_eDK9-LpAe&index=2

Towards Standardized Measurements of Electromagnetic Disturbances from Electric Vehicle Charging Stations

Marco Azpúrua

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Spain*

Sector

Smart grids and smart metering

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

IEC TC 77/SC 77A EMC - Low-frequency phenomena, WG9

Role

Member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

The central gap being addressed is the lack of standardized measurement methods for measuring electromagnetic disturbances in the supraharmonic frequency range (2 kHz – 150 kHz). Existing standards are limited to low-frequency harmonics and do not adequately address the challenges posed by supraharmonics. Therefore, the priority is to develop standardized methods and procedures for measuring electromagnetic disturbances, ensuring electromagnetic compatibility that may lead to revising the IEC 61000-4-30 revision. Creating, validating, and standardising reliable measurement methods for supraharmonic emissions in a relatively short timeframe involves technical and logistical challenges, particularly when experimental validation is needed. Likewise, it is important to promote the adoption of state-of-the-art measurement techniques and facilitate the transfer of technical knowledge through workshops, reports, and collaboration with standardisation bodies to ensure widespread implementation and support of the proposal made. A key strategy for that is achieving good coordination across stakeholders: aligning interests and fostering collaboration among National Metrology Institutes, EVCS manufacturers, charge point operators, and standardisation bodies is essential.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

This fellowship aims to contribute significantly to the ICT standards landscape by addressing technical and knowledge gaps in measurement methodologies, standardisation, and interoperability related to EMC and power quality in EVCS. By developing methods for evaluating electromagnetic disturbances in the 2 kHz–150 kHz range, the project directly supports the development and revision of IEC 61000-4-30 and EN 50065. This ensures that EVCS technology aligns with harmonized requirements.

The activities around the experimental validation of new methods and procedures address a fundamental need within the ICT standards community, where technical decisions may be delayed due to a lack of empirical evidence. By providing validated procedures, I plan to support working groups like IEC SC77A WG9 with the tools needed to bridge the gaps identified between theoretical models and practical implementation, enabling the ICT standards landscape to keep pace with the rapid evolution of EVCS technology.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

This action has the potential to positively impact SMEs and European society by addressing the challenges identified in the EV charging infrastructure. For SMEs, developing standardized procedures and traceable measurement methods creates market opportunities, enabling SMEs to design and manufacture products that meet regulatory requirements more efficiently. Moreover, the project's focus on reliability in EVCS can increase consumer trust in SME-produced technologies, enhancing competitiveness. The project supports the transition to electromobility for European society, aligning with EU environmental goals. A better standardized EVCS facilitates sustainable mobility growth and ensures grid stability while providing solutions for electromagnetic disturbances and power quality issues. This minimizes the risks of power outages and ensures a consistent supply for all consumers. Also, the project strengthens end-user protection by ensuring accurate energy billing.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

My fellowship does not directly contribute to standardisation work; the main objective of this project is to support the development of standardized measurements of electromagnetic disturbances from EVCS, which could potentially impact the revision of IEC 61000-4-30.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, resulting from this project, a public technical paper with results from a measurement campaign will be published.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

This fellowship tackles some complicated objectives that require building a strong knowledge base and investigation. The first steps of this activity were:

- ▶ Literature and standard survey. Conduct a literature review on existing procedures, methods, and instrumentation for detecting conducted interference problems caused by EVCS.
- ▶ Conduct market research to identify affordable and compact/portable EMI measuring instruments suitable for on-site implementation of the proposed methods.
- ▶ Collaboration with EU-funded R&D Projects. Synergies with metrology-related EU-funded R&D projects to gather information on state-of-the-art emissions measurement methods.

The outcome of the first two tasks has been beneficial and part of implementing a prototype of a measurement system of supraharmmonic emissions that I plan to use to demonstrate the methods being developed or improved.

Online references related to the fellowship work

www.iec.ch/dyn/www/f?p=103:7:0:::FSP_ORG_ID,FSP_LANG_ID:1384,25

5. Societal challenges

IoT Semantic Interoperability for Active Assisted Living with robots for enhanced well-being

Amelie Gyrard

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France*

Sector

eHealth

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO/IEC 30197 ED1 IoT for stress management, good health and well-being (follow up and contributions)
IEEE P1872.3 Standard for Ontology Reasoning on Multiple Robots

Role

Member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

My fellowship focus is to make sure that semantic interoperability and standards related to Active Assisted Living (AAL) with robots for enhanced well-being are aligned, it will provide an analysis on the many well-being standardisation initiatives from a semantic interoperability perspective, identify gaps and recommendations for better synergy. This will be achieved by monitoring AAL, robots and well-being standards from different SDOs and contributing when possible.

The objective of the proposed activity is to include European contributions on viable methodologies on semantic interoperability in ISO standards: ISO SC41 IoT and Digital Twin, IEEE Robotics with a focus on practical use cases in the domains of Active Assisted Living with robots for enhanced well-being .

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

This fellowship supports my engagement in several standardisation projects. Especially the standard under development: IEEE P1872.3 Standard for Ontology Reasoning on Multiple Robots as well as ongoing standardisation work at ISO/TC 299 Robotics and IEEE Robotics Standards. In this scope, I contribute to ensuring coordination of standardisation efforts on robotics and autonomous systems in Europe, promoting interaction of all stakeholders considering their vision and real needs (i.e. through public-private partnerships), while engaging on an international level to lead and export the EU's objectives. I am working on several related standards, including:

- ▷ ISO/IEC 30197 ED1 IoT for stress management, good health and well-being: follow up and contributions
- ▷ IEC SyC AAL: investigate standards from this WG
- ▷ ISO 299 Robotics: investigate standards from this WG)
- ▷ IEEE P1872.3 Standard for Ontology Reasoning on Multiple Robots: follow up and collaboration with the team

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

Trialog is a SME so we are directly impacted by my contribution. Trialog was the coordinator of the ACCRA H2020 project (robots for ageing) which is now finished. We follow up with standard activities on robotics. In addition, the standards under consideration will benefit all the Smart Robotics and Internet of Robotic Things ecosystem, including SMEs. SME can develop tools, applications compliant with those standards.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

Yes, with this fellowship, I contribute especially to revising one standard, IEEE P1872.3 Standard for Ontology Reasoning on Multiple Robots, and developing a new one, ISO/IEC 30197 ED1 IoT for stress management, good health and well-being.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

In relation to this fellowships, I have contributed to the Landscape and Gap Analysis For Robotics Collaboration between Adra-e & StandICT.eu 2026¹².

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

I contribute following the meetings and working documents especially of IEEE P1872.3 Standard for Ontology Reasoning on Multiple Robots that will not be officially released before 2026.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/1872.3/11037/>

 <https://www.iso.org/standard/53317.html>

¹² <https://www.standict.eu/landscape-analysis-report/landscape-robotics-standards>

Advancing AI and Health Standards: Harmonizing Information Interoperability and AI for Healthcare

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Spain*

Sector

eHealth

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

ISO/IEC JTC1/SC 42/JWG 3 Joint Working Group ISO/IEC JTC1/SC42 -
ISO/TC215 WG: AI-enabled health informatics

Role

Member

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

The project addresses a central issue in integrating artificial intelligence (AI) in healthcare: the urgent need to harmonize standards that enable the safe and effective use of these technologies in clinical settings. Despite progress made in previous initiatives, such as the initial alignment of FHIR with key international standards, significant challenges remain in the interoperability of systems and the design of regulatory frameworks that are genuinely applicable in day-to-day clinical practice.

One of the most critical gaps is the lack of specific standards for using reliable AI language models in electronic health records. Without this foundation, integrating AI into healthcare systems is limited and potentially risky for patients and professionals. In addition, the increasing complexity of healthcare data demands special attention to privacy and security, areas where compliance with regulations such as the GDPR, AI Act, and Data Act remains a constant challenge.

At this point in the project, the work done so far to map standards setting a roadmap for interoperability remains an essential step, but work remains to be done to translate these proposals into tangible and sustainable results.

The key will be to focus on collaborative work in SDOs such as ISO and HL7, ensuring that new regulations not only respond to technical needs but also align with the fundamental ethical principles of healthcare.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

With this fellowship, I contribute to the ICT standards landscape by advancing and harmonising key standards related to artificial intelligence in healthcare. This effort focuses on ISO ISO/IEC PWI 22989-2, which defines AI concepts and terminology in the healthcare sector, and ISO/IEC AWI TR 18988, which addresses the application of AI technologies in healthcare informatics.

In particular, my fellowship project seeks to integrate generalist AI linguistic models (LLMs) in electronic health records (EHRs), ensuring their interoperability and compliance with

international clinical information standards such as HL7-FHIR, ISO 13606, and ISO 13940. The analysis developed so far has identified the key issues to be considered in these LLMs to incorporate them into the aforementioned projects under development (ISO/IEC PWI 22989-2 and ISO/IEC AWI TR 18988).

The preliminary roadmap developed and in place to date sets out clear strategies for future harmonisation between AI and health information standards, aligning this effort with the effective implementation of the already underway European Health Data Space (EHDS). This progress positions Europe as a global leader in health AI standardisation and lays the foundation for an interoperable and ethically focused ecosystem.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

The project lays the foundation for an accessible and efficient ecosystem around AI in healthcare. Harmonising standards such as FHIR and ISO 13606 reduce technical barriers, enabling SMEs to develop solutions compatible with existing systems and compete with large enterprises. It also lowers development costs and drives innovation.

Impact on Society

For society, AI standardisation promises to improve quality, safety, and equity in healthcare. It will foster public trust through compliance with ethical and privacy principles aligned with European values such as transparency. These improvements can translate into more accurate diagnoses and personalized treatments, benefiting patients and professionals.

The project also boosts the adoption of European Health Data Space (EHDS) under the GDPR. Addressing ethics in decision-making and algorithm use ensures that European values guide this digital transformation, building a framework that improves AI competitiveness and health outcomes.

Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

I am currently involved in the final development phase of the ISO 24305 Committee, which is proposed as PAS. The standard will be ISO/PAS 24305, "Guidelines for implementing HL7/FHIR based on ISO 13940 and ISO 13606."

In parallel, I am a contributor representing UNE in the projects ISO/IEC AWI TR 18988 "Artificial intelligence - Application of AI technologies in healthcare informatics" and ISO/IEC 22989-2 "Information technology - AI - Concepts and terminology - Part 2: Healthcare".

I also intend to contribute to the new ISO/IEC NP 25590 project "Information technology - Artificial intelligence - Guidance for output data quality of generative AI applications," proposed by ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42, which is under voting and whose draft is in the preparatory phase. Although it is not a Health or Healthcare-specific standard, it will be the key international standard for the use of generative AI in Healthcare.

Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables?

Yes, I contribute to drafting technical reports of the related standardisation projects and a roadmap report to harmonize health information standards with AI standards.

What future efforts or activities are still necessary for your area of application?

The initial revision of ISO/CD PAS 24305 was completed and is now in a new iteration in which changes are being finalized at the request of the ISO secretariat. In addition, I am working on contributions to the drafts of ISO/IEC PWI 22989-2 and ISO/IEC AWI TR 18988. Also, a roadmap is being developed to harmonize health information standards with AI based on the work of ISO/TC 215. This progress positions this fellowship project as a key contributor to AI's secure

and efficient integration in the European healthcare environment.

Online references related to the fellowship work

 <https://www.iso.org/committee/6794475.html>

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